

Bones of dinosaurs and other reptiles from the Triassic-Jurassic of the Connecticut Valley: Over 200 years of published history

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Abstract

The bones from the Connecticut Valley in eastern USA came from the Newark Supergroup with the Lower Jurassic remains coming from the uppermost red sandstone bed (Portland Formation, Middle Hettangian) in Connecticut, and the Longmeadow Formation in Massachusetts. The dinosaurs mostly represent herbivorous or omnivorous facultatively bipedal early sauropodomorph non-eusauropod (“prosauropod”) dinosaurs. Two fragmentary records of animals with a body length of ~1.5 m were discovered during blasting for a water well. The first (YPM VP 2125), in 1818 from East Windsor, Conn., is the earliest published record of a North American dinosaur. The second (AMC 41104), in 1855 from Springfield, Mass., is the holotype of *Megadactylus polyzelus* Hitchcock, 1865, which was the type species of *Anchisaurus* Marsh, 1885. In the 1880s, three articulated skeletons came from a quarry in Manchester, Conn. YPM VP 209, the type of *Anchisaurus solus* Marsh, 1892, is a poorly preserved juvenile skeleton (body length ~1 m) with a fragmentary skull. YPM VP 1883, an almost complete well-preserved skeleton (body length 1.6 m) with skull but no tail, is the type of *Anchisaurus colurus* Marsh, 1891. YPM VP 208, the largest specimen (body length 2.5 m), consisting mostly of the hip region and hindlimbs, is *Anchisaurus major* Marsh, 1889, the type species of *Ammosaurus* Marsh, 1891. Long identified as an early carnivorous coelurosaurian theropod dinosaur, *Ammosaurus* is now regarded as a basal sauropodomorph dinosaur and usually as a subjective junior synonym of *Anchisaurus*. However, based on differences in the proximal end of the pubis, with a plesiomorphic closed obturator foramen in YPM VP 208 and an autapomorphic open one in YPM VP 1883 with a triangular sutural surface for the ischium, these are valid sister taxa that constitute the Anchisauridae Marsh, 1885. Other autapomorphies or unique characters for *Anchisaurus* are a postorbital with a transversely expanded ventral process, a lateral pit on the ventral part of the quadrate, and three small foramina in a vertical row ventrally on the proximal part of sacral rib 2. Autapomorphies for *Ammosaurus* include a depression ventrally on the proximal part of sacral rib 2, and no connection beyond the bases of the transverse process and the sacral rib of sacral vertebra 3. YPM VP 2125 may represent a second specimen of *Ammosaurus* based on the hatchet-shaped form of the deltoid process of the humerus and the robust form of distal tarsal 1 and carpal 1. Because of the inadequate nature of the holotype (AMC 41104), YPM VP 1883 was designated by the ICZN (2015) as the neotype of *Megadactylus polyzelus* Hitchcock, 1865, the type species of *Anchisaurus* Marsh, 1885. Three different dispersal events brought the Lower Jurassic basal sauropodomorphs (Anchisauridae, *Seitaard*, *Sarhsaurus*) to North America. Unlike footprints, the bones of carnivorous theropod dinosaurs are very rare. There are two coelophysoid grade skeletons, that of *Podokesaurus holyokensis* Talbot, 1911 from near South Hadley, Mass., a fairly complete skeleton (body length ~1.15 m) but no skull, and a natural cast of the pubis, tibia and ribs of a larger individual (~2.5 to 3 m) from Middletown, Conn. After burial, the bones of the latter were removed by dissolution and the cavities filled with sand. The difficulty distinguishing such sandstone casts of bones from the surrounding sandstone is one reason why skeletal remains are so rare in the region compared to those of footprints. Two isolated, *Dilophosaurus*-like theropod teeth, from the lower Shuttle Meadow Formation in North Guildford, Conn., represent an animal about 4 m long. These teeth are the earliest dinosaur remains from the Connecticut Valley, occurring a little above the End-Triassic Extinction. McMenamin (2021a) describes the distal humerus (width 123 mm) of a large 9 m long supposed theropod dinosaur from the Portland Formation near Amherst, Mass. However, the EDS spectrum shows mostly silica and oxygen, with only trace amounts of phosphorus and calcium, so it is not bone but some version of silica. McMenamin (2021b) also describes the wrist region of a supposed pterosaur from South Hadley, Mass. but clear labelled drawings and photos are needed to establish the identity of this specimen. Hitchcock (1836, 1858, 1865) described the abundant three toed footprints from the Connecticut Valley as “ornithichnites” that were

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presumed to be the tracks of large ground living flightless birds. The genus *Anchisauripus* Lull, 1904a was erected for footprints supposedly made by the prosauropod *Anchisaurus*, but they were probably made by a small *Coelophys*-like theropod dinosaur. However, trackways of *Otozoum* were made by a prosauropod walking with a more plantigrade posture than the prosauropod *Plateosaurus*. The identification of trackways of the brontozoid ichnotaxa *Anchisauripus-Eubrontes-Gigantipus* continuum as those of prosauropods requires a nearly complete lack of correspondence between pad structure and osteology. However, there is an excellent fit between the pes of the theropod dinosaur *Dilophosaurus wetherilli* from Arizona (Lower Jurassic, Kayenta Formation) and the pes reconstructed for *Eubrontes*. The predominance of footprints of carnivorous theropod dinosaurs from the early Early Jurassic of Eastern (and Western) North America may indicate an extremely unusual, inverted food pyramid, with the terrestrial carnivorous theropods probably feeding mostly on fish. By the late Early Jurassic to Middle Jurassic, herbivorous dinosaurs became much more numerous (as indicated by both skeletal fossils and footprints around the world) and normal terrestrial food pyramids were widely established.

The only non-dinosaurian record from the Lower Jurassic of the Connecticut Valley is a partial skeleton from the Longmeadow Sandstone near Longmeadow, Mass. This is *Stegomus longiceps* Emerson & Loomis, 1904, the type species of the protosuchian crocodylomorph *Stegomosuchus* Huene, 1922. This small (body length 25 to 30 cm, a juvenile) agile, cursorial, carnivorous animal is correlated with the ichnotaxon *Batrachopus gracilis*.

Several different non-dinosaurian remains have been discovered in the Upper Triassic (pre-latest Rhaetian) from the New Haven Formation of the Hartford basin, Conn. A partial right scapula (estimated animal's body length ~225 cm) was found in 1888 in Simsbury. Described as *Rutiodon validus* (Marsh, 1893), it is an indeterminate phytosaur, a group of aquatic predators resembling living crocodiles. A natural mold of the underside of 16 plates of the dorsal part of the dermal armor (body length ~150 cm) was found in 1895 in Fair Haven. *Stegomus arcuatus* Marsh, 1896b is referred to the Aetosauria, a group of quadrupedal herbivorous reptiles. The pseudosuchian *Erpetosuchus* is represented by a skull found in Cheshire in 1995. It was a small (body length ~61 cm), lightly built, cursorial predator. The parareptilian procolophonid *Hypsognathus fennert* is represented by a mold of the anterior part of the body with an almost complete skull as bone, was found in 1967 in Meriden. The molar-like teeth, with the deep cheek region and deep lower jaws, indicate that it fed on tough high fiber plant material. A small partial skull (body length >1 m), found in 1965 in central Connecticut, was named *Colopops noviportensis* Pritchard *et al.*, 2018 as the most basal rhynchosaur. However, Scheyer *et al.* (2020) note that the dorso-ventrally compressed and disarticulated bones are those of the skull of a normal rhynchocephalian lepidosauromorph, not a rhynchosaur, and that the supposed reinforced snout and exceptionally enlarged temporal region (indicative of very large jaw closing muscles) are artifacts of preservation.

Keywords

Dinosauria, Sauropodomorpha, Archosauria, Lower Jurassic, Upper Triassic.

1. INTRODUCTION

The history is given for each of the few specimens with bones from the Lower Jurassic and the underlying Upper Triassic of the Connecticut Valley, that extends from south to north through central Connecticut and into the adjacent part of southern Massachusetts (for map of sites see Lull, 1915, 1953: 67-68; general accounts McDonald, 1992, 2010; detailed accounts Getty *et al.*, 2017; Olsen, 2017a, b). These specimens came from the Newark Supergroup with most of the Jurassic dinosaur remains coming from the uppermost red sandstone bed, the Portland Formation (=Sandstone) in Connecticut, and the Longmeadow Formation (=Sandstone) in Massachusetts (Fig. 1A). These rocks were long regarded as Upper Triassic but more recently they were referred to the Lower Jurassic (Cornet *et al.*, 1973; Cornet & Traverse, 1975; Olsen & Galton, 1977; Olsen *et al.*, 1982; now middle Hettangian, ~200.5 Ma, Olsen, 2017a: 31). Two theropod teeth from North Guildford, Conn., from the lower Shuttle Meadow Formation (Fig. 1A) a little above the End Triassic Extinction event at 201.3 to 201.0 Ma, are the earliest record of dinosaurs from the Connecticut Valley. The Triassic non-dinosaurian bones were found in the Hartford basin in Connecticut, coming from the underlying part of the Newark Supergroup, the

New Haven Formation (=Arkose, Fig. 1A; latest Triassic, just before the End Triassic Extinction event in latest Rhaetian, 201.564 Ma, Olsen, 2017a: 16).

An update is provided to the section on reptilian bones from the Connecticut Valley by Lull (1953), who reproduced many of the drawings and quoted extensively (often completely) from most of the earlier descriptions published in English and provided additional documentation. The few skeletal remains of dinosaurs discovered in the 1800s in the Lower Jurassic of North America came from the Connecticut Valley. In present-day terminology, they mostly represent herbivorous (plant-eating) or omnivorous (mixed diet) facultatively (optionally) bipedal early sauropodomorph ("prosauropod") non-eusauropod dinosaurs (Fig. 1B). Bones of carnivorous (meat-eating) bipedal theropod dinosaurs are even less common, those of herbivorous ornithischians are non-existent, and the only non-dinosaurian reptile is a small terrestrial basal protosuchian crocodyliform. Dates and bibliographical details for the important researchers on the bones from the Connecticut Valley are given at the end of this paper, along with the acknowledgements.

2. MUSEUM ABBREVIATIONS

AMC, Amherst College Museum, now the Beneski Museum of Natural History, Amherst, MA, USA; **AMNH**, American Museum of Natural History, New York, NY, USA; **BM**, Bruce Museum, Greenwich, CT, USA; **BMOS**, Boston Museum of Science, Boston, MA, USA; **BSNH**, Boston Society of Natural History, Boston, MA, USA; **DSP**, Dinosaur State Park, Rocky Hill, CT, USA; **MNA**, Museum of Northern Arizona, Flagstaff, AZ, USA; **MPEF**, Museo Paleontológico Egidio Feruglio, Trelew, Argentina; **NM**, National Museum, Bloemfontein, South Africa; **SAM**, South African Museum, Cape Town, South Africa; **SMP**, State Museum of Pennsylvania, Harrisburg, PA, USA; **UCMP**, Museum of Paleontology, University of California, Berkeley, CA, USA; **YPM VP**, Division of Vertebrate Paleontology, Peabody Museum of Natural History, Yale University, New Haven, CT, USA; **YPM VP P**, Vertebrate Paleontology Collection, formerly of Princeton University Museum of Natural History, Princeton, NJ, USA, now housed at YPM.

3. LOWER JURASSIC SKELETAL REMAINS – SAURISCHIA

3.1. Early Sauropodomorpha (“Prosauropoda”: Table 1)

3.1.1. Articulated specimens in fragments, the result of blasting for wells

3.1.1.1. YPM VP 2125 from East Windsor, Conn. (Fig. 1C-N)

The earliest discovery of a “prosauropod” or basal sauropodomorph member (Fig. 1B) of the Dinosauria of Owen (1842; Latin “fearfully great lizard”) occurred in 1818 during blasting operations in the red sandstone of the Portland Formation (Fig. 1A) for a water well near Ketch’s Mills in the eastern part of East Windsor (map locality 30, Lull, 1953: 68). After the blast, fragmentary remains of what was probably a complete skeleton were spotted in the resulting debris. Unfortunately, many pieces were taken away as souvenirs by onlookers or were missed. Consequently, only a few pieces were recovered and some of these were donated to the Museum of Yale College in New Haven by Benjamin Silliman, Sr. He was one of the founders of the *American Journal of Science*, an important vehicle for publication of papers on the geology and paleontology of the Connecticut Valley. These fragmentary remains, collected by Solomon Ellsworth, Jr., were reported by Nathan Smith (1820a, b), who mentioned that the remains might be human. However, this possibility was strongly disputed by Dr E. D. Porter (in Hall, 1821: 247), who noted that the “tail bone was easily discovered by its numerous articulations

distinctly visible when the bones were first obtained; and by its being projected, in a curvilinear direction beyond the general mass.” He noted that the tail projected about 18 inches (45.72 cm) beyond the main mass and he gave a specimen, easily distinguished by its numerous articulations, to Hitchcock (1823: 43). Silliman provided three bone fragments for sketching by Hitchcock (1841: 505, pl. 49, figs 66-68; as Figs 1C-E), who earlier identified these remains as reptilian (Hitchcock, 1835: 237).

The fragmentary remains of YPM VP 2125 (body length ~1.5 m; Figs 1F-N), the only surviving remains from near Ketch’s Mills, were described as reptilian by Wyman (1855), who studied anatomy under Richard Owen of the British Museum, London while in Europe in 1841-1842 (Wilder, 1875). It was identified as dinosaurian by Marsh (1896a: 146), and referred to *Anchisaurus colurus* by Lull (1912, 1915) and Huene (1914a), who in 1932 referred it to *Yalesaurus colurus*, as did Lull (1953) (for details see Section 3.1.2). The partial forelimb (Figs 1F-H) was finally illustrated and identified as Prosauropoda *incertae sedis* by Galton (1976, fig. 32; Fig. 1G). The proximal portion of the humerus (Figs 1F, G; for keys to bones of limbs and girdles, see Figs 4G, H, 6N, 11R) is compressed but part of the shaft extends alongside the deltopectoral crest (d, Fig. 1G), so this is a medial (internal) view of the right humerus. The forelimb (Figs 1F, G) is intermediate in size between AMC 41104 and YPM VP 1883 (cf. Figs 4A, G, 11I). The distal part of the left femur (Figs 1I, J; cf. Figs 3P-U, 4G) has a maximum width of ~40 mm, and there are traces of the adjacent proximal ends of the tibia and fibula. There are four small blocks containing fragmentary remains of articulated middle to distal tail vertebrae (Figs 1K-N). The existing bones (Figs 1F-N) of the East Windsor find are important because, although fragmentary and not recognized as such when originally described, they are the first non-avian dinosaur skeletal remains to be described from North America. This specimen represents the earliest sauropodomorph (“prosauropod”) and one of the earliest dinosaurs to be described from anywhere in the world. It also provides additional evidence for a second taxon of early sauropodomorph in the Lower Jurassic of the Connecticut Valley (see Section 3.1.9).

3.1.1.2. AMC 41104 from Springfield, Mass. (Figs 1S, 2, 3, 4A-C)

In 1855, Edward B. Hitchcock, Sr. reported the discovery and acquisition for Amherst College of bones from Springfield, Mass. They represent parts of another probably complete skeleton that was shattered during a blasting operation in 1855 (Ostrom, 1971; Tweet *et al.*, 2010; Tweet & Santucci, 2011; Santucci, 2012). This time, it involved excavations for a well for the casting of a big gun at the “Water Shops” at Mill Pond (close

Table 1. Summary of the completeness and sizes of the specimens of early sauropodomorphs from the Connecticut Valley along with their taxonomic history.

Specimen	Completeness	Measurements	Previous taxonomic opinions	Current taxonomic opinion
YPM VP 2125	Fragmentary remains of caudal vertebrae, the distal end of the left femur, and fragmentary right forelimb.	Estimated body length: 1.5 m	<i>Anchisaurus colurus</i> (Lull, 1912, 1915; von Huene, 1914a) <i>Yaleosaurus colurus</i> (von Huene, 1932; Lull, 1953)	cf. <i>Ammosaurus major</i>
AMC 41104	Eleven vertebrae, incomplete scapula, partial manus, ischia and incomplete hind limb.	Femoral length: 178 mm Estimated body length: 1.5 m	<i>Megadactylus polyzelus</i> (Hitchcock, 1865; Cope, 1870b). <i>Amphisaurus polyzelus</i> (Marsh, 1877) belonging to Amphisauridae (Marsh, 1882). <i>Anchisaurus polyzelus</i> (Marsh, 1885) belonging to Anchisauridae in Theropoda (Marsh, 1885).	Unidentified sauropodomorph, aff. <i>Efraasia diagnostica</i>
YPM VP 208	Incomplete left scapula, the three posterior dorsal vertebrae and sacrum, the pelvic girdle and partial hind limb bones.	Femoral length: over 280 mm Estimated body length: 2.5 m	<i>Anchisaurus major</i> (Marsh, 1889). <i>Ammosaurus major</i> (Marsh, 1891). <i>Ammosaurus major</i> belonging to Ornithopoda (von Huene, 1906). <i>Ammosaurus major</i> belonging to Thecodontosauridae (von Huene, 1907).	<i>Ammosaurus major</i> (holotype)
YPM VP 6282	Several dorsal ribs			Archosauria
YPM VP 1883	Skull, cervicals 2 to 3, dorsal vertebrae, right forelimb, partial right hind limb.	Femoral length: 180 mm Estimated body length: 1.6 m	<i>Anchisaurus colurus</i> (holotype, Marsh, 1885), and type species of <i>Anchisaurus</i> . <i>Yaleosaurus colurus</i> (holotype, von Huene, 1914a), and type species of <i>Yalesaurus</i> . <i>Megadactylus polyzelus</i> (neotype of <i>Anchisaurus</i> , ICZN 2015).	<i>Anchisaurus polyzelus</i> (neotype, adult)
YPM VP 209	Almost complete skeleton, missing only the distal part of the tail and the right forelimb.	Femoral length: 110 mm Estimated body length: 1 m	<i>Anchisaurus solus</i> (Marsh, 1892)	<i>Anchisaurus polyzelus</i> (referred, juvenile)

Fig. 1. A, Stratigraphic nomenclature in the Hartford sub-basin part of the Connecticut Valley Rift Basin (after Hubert *et al.*, 1976). The solid black represents the basaltic formations; the scale is in Km with 0 at the End Triassic Extinction event at the latest Rhaetian, 201.564 Ma (Olsen, 2017a: 16) – rocks above this are Lower Jurassic with Upper Triassic below it. Only part of the Portland (*, Longmeadow Formation in Massachusetts) and New Haven formations are included. B, Phylogenetic relationships of the North American Jurassic basal sauropodomorphs, modified from Rowe *et al.* (2010) for their augmented matrix of Upchurch *et al.* (2007). With the recognition of *Ammosaurus* as a valid genus distinct from *Anchisaurus*, these genera form the Anchisauridae. C-N: basal sauropodomorph dinosaur *incertae sedis* from East Windsor, Conn., possibly referable to *Ammosaurus* (see Section 3.1.9), YPM VP 2125. C-E: from Hitchcock, 1841, specimens lost; C, section of caudal vertebra; D, uncertain and E, transverse section of a long bone. F-H: incomplete right forelimb in lateral view, F, bones; G, outline modified from Galton (1976) and H, detail of bones of wrist region. I-J: distal end of femur in I, side and J, anterior views. K-N: middle and distal caudal vertebrae in lateral view. O-R: natural sandstone casts of bones from Ellington, Conn. (from Hitchcock, 1841, specimens lost): O, shaft of dorsal rib in two views; P-R: proximal ends of tibiae in P, posterior and Q, R, lateral views. S, restoration of right manus in lateral view of basal sauropodomorph dinosaur *Anchisaurus* (*Megadactylus*) *polyzelus* Hitchcock, 1865, AMC 41/109 (now AMC 41104, former holotype, replaced by neotype YPM VP 1883, Fig. 6) from Longmeadow Formation of Springfield, Mass., from Hitchcock (1865). Photographs by PMG; Abbreviations: d, deltopectoral crest; D, distal tarsal; 1-5, metacarpals 1 to 5; H, humerus; R, radius; U, ulna; scale bars = 15 mm (C-E), 25 mm (F-H, S), 10 mm (I-N) and 50 mm (O-R).

to Mill River) at the United States Armory (Santucci, 1998, fig. 1 for armory; map locality 27, Lull, 1953: 67). These bones occurred in the same level and type of rock, a thick-bedded, coarse-gritted, red sandstone (now the Longmeadow Formation or Sandstone, *, Fig. 1A), as the find from Ketch's Mills (Hitchcock, 1858). This specimen (AMC 41/109, now 41104, Figs 1S, 2, 3, 4A-C; femoral length ~178 mm, body length ~1.5 m) was found by William Smith. It was briefly described without a name by Wyman (in Hitchcock, 1858: 187), who commented on the reptilian form of the femur and caudal vertebrae and especially on the hollowness of all the bones. Hitchcock (1858: 187) noted that these bones showed "that large reptiles lived in the Connecticut Valley in sandstone days; and this, also, was one of the

most common sort of animals, judging by the tracks." On the previous page, he also noted that "these (saurian) animals (from Ketch's Mills, East Windsor) are fair representatives of those that made the tracks". These comments are particularly interesting because Hitchcock (1836), who originally described the Connecticut Valley footprints as "ornithichnites", advocated for the rest of his life that the tridactyl footprints were made by large ground living flightless birds like the extinct moas of New Zealand (*Dinornis*, Owen, 1843a) and the living ostrich (*Struthio camelus*) of southern Africa (but with three toes rather than two as in the ostrich). However, within four months of the 1836 publication, Richard Owen wrote Hitchcock that the tracks may have been produced by bipedal reptiles (Hitchcock, 1841: 517;

Fig. 2. Early sauropodomorph dinosaur *Anchisaurus* (*Megadactylus*) *polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865) from Longmeadow Formation of Springfield, Mass., AMC 41/109 (now AMC 41104, former holotype, neotype is YPM VP 1883, Fig. 6), modified from Cope (1870b). A-D: left femur in A, posterior view (restored too long, cf. Fig. 3O); B, proximal end in anterior view; C-D: distal end in C, distal and D, anterior views. E, proximal end of left fibula in posterior view. F, distal part of left fibula with calcaneum (since lost) in posterior view. G, as F plus metatarsal IV in lateral view. H-I: left tibia in H, lateral and I, proximal views. J-L: distal part of ischia in J, anteroventral; K, right lateral and L, distal views. M, restored right manus in lateral view. N, proximal part of cervical ribs in lateral view. O-P: centra of dorsal vertebrae in O, ventral and P, lateral views. Q, two incomplete proximal caudal vertebrae and a chevron in left lateral view. R, two incomplete distal caudal vertebrae in right lateral view. Scale bar = 50 mm.

Robinson, 1979: 69). Surprisingly enough, although Owen (1842) created the Dinosauria and commented on the three-toed footprints from the Connecticut Valley several times, he never suggested in print that they were made by dinosaurs. This was because he attributed them to early representatives of birds of a low grade of organization, remnants of which were represented by the extinct moas (*Dinornis*) and the extant Brown Kiwi (*Apteryx australis*) of New Zealand, with some species of the former being large enough to have made footprints the size of *Ornithichnites giganteus* (Owen, 1843a, b, 1845, 1849; Silliman, 1843). The discovery of quadrupedal trackways, and ones with tail impressions, led Field (1860) to assert that all the bird-like tracks

were reptilian. Hitchcock (1863, 1865) found support for the tracks being those of birds from Owen's (1863) description of the foot of the first complete skeleton of the ancestral bird *Archaeopteryx* from the Upper Jurassic of Germany. However, Cope (1867a: 30) noted that "creatures of the form of *Laelaps*, *Iguanodon*, and *Hadrosaurus* [i.e., dinosaurs], would amply account for the well-known foot-tracks of the Triassic Red Sandstone of the Connecticut Valley" and, subsequently, that the most bird-like footprints were made by a genus nearly allied to *Laelaps* (Cope, 1867b: 234; now theropod dinosaur *Dryptosaurus*, Upper Cretaceous, New Jersey; see Brusatte *et al.*, 2011).

In 1865, Edward B. Hitchcock, Jr. of Amherst College,

Fig. 3. Early sauropodomorph dinosaur *Anchisaurus* (*Megadactylus*) *polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865) from Longmeadow Formation of Springfield, Mass., AM 41/109 (now AM 41104, former holotype, neotype is YPM VP 1883, Figs 6A-C). A-B: centrum of last dorsal vertebra in A, anterior and B, left lateral views. C, centrum of first sacral vertebrae in ventral view. D-E: two proximal caudal vertebrae in D, anterior and E, left lateral views. F-G: proximal left scapula in F, anterior and G, lateral views. H-L: right manus, H, restored in lateral (dorsal) view (see Galton, 1976, figs 7L, M for stereo photographs of two sides as preserved); I, radius and ulna in distal view; J, digit 1 in ventral view; K, digit 1 phalanges in lateral view. L, digit 1 phalanges in medial view. M-O: distal ischia in M, right lateral; N, dorsal and O, distal views. P-U: left femur in P, lateral; Q, posterior; R, medial; S, anterior; T, proximal and U, distal views. V, left fibula, calcaneum and metatarsal 4 in lateral view. W-X: left tibia in W, lateral and X, proximal views. Y, proximal right metatarsal 2 in lateral view. Modified from Galton (1976) which has additional views and bones. Abbreviations: C, calcaneum; ch, chevron; cn, cnemial crest; F, fibula; he, head; ic, inner or medial condyle; les, lesser trochanter; M, metacarpal I; M1, insertion area for caudifemoralis brevis muscle; M2, insertion area for caudifemoralis longus muscle; oc, outer or lateral condyle; R, radius; sa r, facet for sacral rib 1; tp, surface for transverse process; U, ulna; 4 tr, fourth trochanter; 1-5, digits 1-5. Scale bar = 40 mm (A-L) and 50 mm (M-Y).

the first physical-health educator at an American university, figured the manus (Fig. 1S) of AMC 41104. After quoting from comments in a letter from Richard Owen, with whom he stayed during 1860-1861 as a private pupil studying anatomy, Hitchcock named the specimen *Megadactylus polyzelus* (Greek for “big digit” as suggested by Owen, “much sought for” – a reference to rarity of the occurrence of bones compared to those of footprints in the Connecticut Valley). *Megadactylus* was first recognized as a dinosaur by Cope (1870a) who suggested that it, rather than large ground living birds, made some of the Connecticut Valley footprints. Cope (1870a: 391) noted that “tracks of an animal (from Connecticut Valley Triassic) resting in a plantigrade position, as indicated by the molds of two long parallel metatarsi, each terminated by three toes, are accompanied by a peculiar, bilobate, transversely oval mark on the middle line, some distance behind the heels. The present specimen (AMC 41/109) shows clearly that it was made by the obtuse extremities of the ischia” (Figs 2J-L; also Figs 3M-O 4B, C). The bones of the holotype of *Megadactylus polyzelus* were finally described and illustrated (Fig. 2) by Cope (1870b). Marsh (1877: 344) noted that most of the three-toed “bird tracks” from the Connecticut Valley that he knew of are associated with manus imprints, so they were not made by birds but by quadrupedal dinosaurs walking bipedally. Because the name *Megadactylus* was preoccupied, Marsh (1877: 344) renamed it *Amphisaurus* (Greek for “both lizard”; with Amphisauridae Marsh, 1882). As this generic name was also preoccupied, it became *Anchisaurus* Marsh, 1885 (Greek for “near lizard”), with Anchisauridae Marsh, 1885 as the first valid named family of early sauropodomorphs. However, it was originally included in the Theropoda (“beast foot”) of Marsh (1881), its position in Marsh (1896a) to Colbert (1970). Marsh (1889, 1896a) refigured the manus and ischia of *A. polyzelus* (Figs 4A-C). The specimen was illustrated by Huene (1914a) and more recently by Galton (1976) (Fig. 3), who showed that the proximal part of the ischium (Huene, 1914a, fig. 29; also, Marsh, 1889, 1896a; Fig. 4B) was based on the inverted lower portion of the scapula (Figs 3F, G).

3.1.2. Articulated quarry specimens from Manchester, Connecticut

The most productive bone locality in the Connecticut Valley was a brownstone quarry known for its “redstone”, the Buckland (Wolcott) Quarry about one mile north of Buckland station in Manchester, Conn. (map locality 31, Lull, 1953: 68). The bones occurred in a coarse, red arkosic sandstone (so contains at least 25% feldspar) high in the upper Portland Formation, with the productive layer being about 2.5 ft thick. These sediments were deposited in a setting of ephemeral braided streams with occasional high-energy shallow floods, just west of the

large alluvial fan that formed on the eastern border of the Hartford basin (Hubert *et al.*, 1982). To date, this is the most productive site for described dinosaur skeletons on the East Coast of the USA (for other sites, see Weishampel & Young, 1996), with three well-preserved skeletons of early sauropodomorphs discovered in the 1880s. These skeletons were described as the holotypes of three separate species by Marsh (1889, 1891, 1892, 1893, 1896a).

The notebooks of Othniel Charles Marsh provided information concerning the discovery of the specimens, which Lull summarized (1915: 78, 1953: 61; quoted in Galton, 1976: 6).

1. **Specimen YPM VP 208** (Figs 4L-O, 5, 11S-U, 12A-F, 13J-P, 14C-F; Huene, 1906, 1907-1908; 1914a; 1932; Galton, 1971, 1976; Yates, 2007; Sereno, 2007) represents the largest individual from the quarry (femoral length slightly over 280 mm, body length ~2.5 m). It includes the incomplete left scapula, the three posterior dorsal vertebrae and sacrum, the pelvic girdle and partial hind limb bones. It is the holotype of *Anchisaurus major* Marsh, 1889, the type species of *Ammosaurus* Marsh, 1891 (Greek for “sand lizard”). It was found in 1884 and, before its contents were recognized, the adjacent block of rock, that presumably contained the skull and fore quarters, was supposedly built into the abutments of a bridge over Bigelow Brook in south Manchester. Earnest efforts at that time failed to secure the missing anterior portion. However, there is a conflict in the records because Bigelow Brook passes WE through central Manchester (see Colton, 1965), so a bridge that was constructed at the same time over Hop Brook in south Manchester was an alternative interment site for the missing parts of *Ammosaurus*. After 85 years, the latter bridge was scheduled for demolition for highway improvements (Darnton, 1969). The late John H. Ostrom of Yale University organized a search for bones in the stone blocks from this bridge (Ostrom, 1969a; photos also in Weishampel & Young, 1996, figs 9.11, 9.12). A block containing the missing outer half of the longitudinally sectioned right femur of YPM VP 208 (Fig. 5C) was located, showing that this was the correct bridge! A second block (YPM VP 6282) has pieces of several dorsal ribs that might be “prosauropod” but they cannot be identified more positively than those of a large archosaurian (?dinosaurian) reptile.
2. **Specimen YPM VP 1883** (Figs 4D-K, 6, 8, 9A-F, 10, 11A-R, 12G-N, 13A-I, 14A, B; Huene, 1906, 1914a, 1932, 1956; Lull, 1915, 1953; Galton, 1976, 2012a, b; Yates, 2004, 2007, 2010; Sereno, 2007; Fedak & Galton, 2007) is the neotype of *Megadactylus polyzelus*, Hitchcock, 1865, the type species of *Anchisaurus* Marsh, 1885 and the holotype of *Anchisaurus colurus* Marsh, 1891 (Latin for “short

Fig. 4. Basal sauropodomorph dinosaurs. A-K: *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865), A-C, AMC 41/109, now AMC 41104 (former holotype) from Longmeadow Formation of Springfield, Mass. A, restoration of right manus in anterior or lateral view and B-C: ischia (also in Lull, 1915, 1953) in B, posterodorsal and C, distal views but proximal part based on inverted proximal part of left scapula in posterior view, see Figs 3F, G). D-K: YPM VP 1883, holotype of *A. colurus* Marsh, 1891, neotype of *A. polyzelus*, from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn., D-F: restoration of skull in D, left lateral, E, dorsal and F, posterior (without quadrates or lower jaws) views. G-K: restorations of left side in lateral view: G, fore limb and girdle; H, hind limb and girdle and I-K: complete animal in left lateral view (body length ~1.6 m): I, from Marsh (1893), posterior two thirds of neck and all of tail not preserved in YPM VP 1883 (Figs 6A-C) so restored after YPM VP 209 (Fig. 7), and J-K: as a statuette by R. S. Lull: J, in the flesh (right printed in reverse) and K, from the left side to show skeleton. L-O: *Ammosaurus (Anchisaurus) major* (Marsh, 1889), holotype YPM VP 208, from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn.: L, restoration of right pes in anterior view and M, sacrum with ilia in ventral view; N, left ischium in ventral view (restored anteroventral edge as -----, ilium and pubis deleted; cf. Fig. 5D) and O, left pelvic girdle region and hindlimb shown as preserved in lateral view with ilium supplemented from right one (cf. Figs 5A, 12F). A-I, L, M modified from Marsh (1896a), photographs for J, K by PMG and N, O modified from R. S. Lull in Huene (1907-1908, figs 297, 298). Abbreviations: c, coracoid; f, femur; fi, fibula; h, humerus; il, ilium; is, ischium, m, manus; mc, metacarpal; pes, pes with metatarsals and phalanges (see L); pu, pubis; r, radius; s, scapula; t, tibia, u, ulna; 1, 5, metatarsals (panel O) I and V. Scale bars = 20 mm (A, D-F), 30 mm (B, C), 100 mm (G, H) and 50 mm (L-O).

tail”), the type species of *Yaleosaurus* Huene, 1932 (the “Yale lizard”). It was found in a large block of sandstone 20 ft (6 m) south of the first specimen. The left scapula and humerus (Figs 6A, B, 11E) were exposed for a long time on what was then the outer surface of the wall of the quarry. It represents a medium sized individual (Figs 4I-K, 10A; femoral length ~180 mm, body length ~1.6 m) with an almost complete skull (Figs 4D-F, 8, 9A-F, 10B-G; Galton, 1976; Yates, 2004; Fedak & Galton, 2007) but lacking most of the neck and the tail, but preserving a left girdle and fore limb, and a partial foot reconstructed with plaster. It was the main basis for a skeletal reconstruction of *Anchisaurus* (Fig. 4I) by Marsh (1893, 1896a) that was reproduced most recently by

Colbert (1970). However, as noted by Huene (1906: 107), the ilium in Marsh (1892, 1893, 1896a; Figs 4H, I) was based on that of YPM VP 208 (Figs 4O, 5B, C, 12F). Bakker (1986: 454) noted that the dorsal part of the ilium of YPM VP 1883, with its long anterior process (Fig. 12H), was exposed in 1971 by PMG, but this preparation was actually by the late Peter J. Whybrow (YPM then MCZ) in 1968.

3. **Specimen YPM VP 209** (Figs 7, 9G, H; Huene, 1906, 1914a, 1932, 1956; Galton, 1971, 1976; Fedak & Galton, 2007) was identified as *Anchisaurus solus* Marsh, 1892 and it was found 2 ft (0.61 m) higher and 15 ft (4.57 m) to the southeast of the second specimen. It is an almost complete but poorly preserved skeleton (Fig. 7) of a small juvenile individual (femoral

Fig. 5. Basal sauropodomorph dinosaur *Ammosaurus* (*Anchisaurus*) *major* (Marsh, 1889) from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn., A-F: outline drawings of the main block of the holotype YPM VP 208 as preserved for A-E, the complete block in A, dorsal; B, left lateral (cf. Fig. 4O for equivalent view with ilium based on reversed right ilium, Fig. 12F); C, right lateral and D, ventral views. E, as A to show positions of bones of pelvis and right hind limb. F: sacrum in F, ventral view. G, sacral vertebrae in left lateral view with ribs omitted to show structure of centra, zygapophyses and spinal processes. Abbreviations: a, ACET, acet, acetabulum; ant, anterior or preacetabular process of ilium; AST, astragalus; DOR, dorsal vertebra; MT, metatarsal IV; obt, obt for, obturator foramen; SA 1, dorsosacral (first sacral) vertebra; SA 2, primordial first (second) sacral vertebra; SA 3, primordial second (third) sacral vertebra; SA R 1, rib of dorsosacral (first sacral) vertebra; SA R 2, rib of primordial first (second) sacral vertebra; SA R 3, rib of primordial second (third) sacral vertebra; tr, TR P, transverse process of primordial second (third) sacral vertebra; I-V, metatarsals I-V; 1-4, metatarsals I-IV, metatarsals 1-4; 4th troc, fourth trochanter. A-F modified from Galton (1976, see figs 24A, B, 25 for stereo photographs for A, D, F) and G modified from Huene (1914a). Scale bar = 50 mm.

Fig. 6. Basal sauropodomorph dinosaur *Anchisaurus (Megadactylus) polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865) from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn. (YPM VP 1883, neotype, holotype of *A. colurus* Marsh, 1891. A-B: interpretive line drawing (A, modified from Galton, 1976) and photograph (B, see Galton, 1976, fig. 11 for stereo photograph) of complete specimen with main block mostly in ventral view, right forearm and manus in lateral view [for original position of distal part of complete humerus over proximal ulna see Huene (1906, pl. 3)] and cervical vertebrae 1-3 and skull in dorsal view. C, photograph of right side of main block (left side of skeleton, cf. A, B). D-E, axis and cervical 3 in D, dorsal and E, left lateral views. F-G: dorsal vertebrae in left lateral view: F, dorsal 9 and G, dorsal 13. H-N: right manus: H, in antero-lateral view for digits 1 to 3; I-J, digits 4 and 5 in I, medial view on other side of block (* a hole in matrix visible in H and I) and J, printed in reverse so in “lateral” view. K-M: penultimate phalange and ungual in anterior view for digits: K, first; L, second and M, third. N, manus in lateral view with digit 4 and carpals preserved on medial side of manus [cf. I; modified from Huene (1914a)]. For other photographs of YPM VP 1883, see Huene (1906) and stereo photographs in Galton (1976). Abbreviations: AS, astragalus; CE, cervical vertebra; DC, distal carpals; DOR, dorsal vertebra, MC, metacarpal 3; PH, phalanges SA 1 sacral vertebra; SAR 1, sacral rib 1; 1-5, digits 1-5. A-B modified from Galton (1976), F, G, N from Huene (1914a); photographs B-E and H-M by PMG; scale bars = 50 mm (note ruler is 70 mm in B, C), 20 mm (D-G) and 10 mm (H-N).

length 110 mm at most, body length ~1 m) with a fragmentary disarticulated skull (Figs 9G, H; Fedak & Galton, 2007).

4. **YPM VP Lost**, an isolated large dorsal rib that was found by Marsh in 1894 at the Manchester quarry (since lost, Lull, 1953).

The quarry ceased operations in about 1890 and most of it has been filled in to form part of the parking area for the Buckland Hills Mall, with only a little of the

original quarry remaining (part shown in McDonald, 2010, fig. 5.19).

3.1.3. Studies by Huene and Lull in 1900s-1950s

Many of the specimens from the Connecticut Valley were inadequately described and illustrated, some not at all. Few comparisons were made with specimens

Fig. 7. Basal sauropodomorph dinosaur from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn., juvenile individual, YPM 209, holotype of *Anchisaurus solus* Marsh, 1892. A, C, photographs and B, D, interpretive line drawings of A-B, specimen mostly in ventral view and C-D, posterior half of opposite side of block (with D at slightly larger size) to show rest of skeleton. Modified from Galton (1976), which see for stereo photographs of A and C plus other outline drawings (also Huene, 1914a), see Figs 9G, H for skull after further preparation. Photographs A and C taken by PMG. Abbreviations: C, CA, caudal vertebra; CE, cervical vertebra; DOR, dorsal vertebra; MAND, mandible; 1-4, metatarsals 1 to 4. Scale bars = 100 mm (A-C, note ruler is 70 mm in A, C) and 50 mm (D).

from elsewhere in the world, especially those from the rich reptilian fauna of the Middle Keuper (former Stubensandstein and Knollenmergel, now Löwenstein and Trossingen formations, Upper Triassic, Norian-Rhaetian) of southern Germany (see Sues & Fraser, 2010: 89-95). This lacuna was filled by Friedrich Richard Freiherr von Hoyningen (better known under his “penname” Friedrich von Huene; Maisch, 2021) of Tübingen University, Germany, who published well illustrated descriptions in German between 1906 and 1914 of the reptiles, mostly dinosaurian, of the Connecticut Valley. The Dinosauria or “fearfully great lizards” of Owen (1842) was considered as diphyletic since 1887, when Harry Govier Seeley argued that it consisted of two separate and unrelated groups, the Saurischia (“lizard hipped”) and the Ornithischia (“bird hipped”). Von Huene originally revised the abundant material of the large German “prosauropod” dinosaur *Plateosaurus* (Huene, 1907-1908; see Huene, 1926), which he considered a primitive saurischian. As an extension of this work, Huene (1906) described the remains of *Anchisaurus colurus* based on a poor cast of the main block (cast YPM VP PU 24516 probably from the same mold, D. Brinkman pers. comm. 2018) plus photographs sent to him by Charles E. Beecher (YPM); a new reconstruction of the skull was prepared (also in Huene, 1907-1908, fig. 318). Huene (1906) commented on Cope’s (1870b) figures of *Megadactylus* (Fig. 2), which he referred to the English Upper Triassic genus *Thecodontosaurus* Riley & Stutchbury, 1836 (see Benton *et al.*, 2000; Galton, 2007; Ballell *et al.*, 2020) as *T. polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1856). The bones of *Anchisaurus solus* and *Ammosaurus major* were also described, based on photographs from C. E. Beecher (YPM), and later he reproduced drawings by R. S. Lull (Figs 4N, O) of the pelvic girdle and incomplete hind limb of *A. major* (Huene 1907-1908, figs 297, 298). *Ammosaurus* was originally regarded by Huene (1906) as an ornithopod dinosaur based on its elongate anterior iliac process (Figs 4O, 5B, C, 12A, F). However, in 1907-1908, he noted that it was allied to *Thecodontosaurus antiquus* and *Massospondylus carinatus* in the family Thecodontosauridae (=Anchisauridae *sensu* Marsh, 1885, mentioned as the “5th family of theropods in von Huene, 1907: p. 7). Von Huene’s classification system for Saurischia reflected the paleogeographic reconstructions that he had outlined in 1907 (fig. 301), where a land bridge across the North Atlantic connected North America and Europe, and the Mediterranean occupied a larger basin across the rest of Europe.

Lull (1912) provided the first review of the geology and the fossil record of the Connecticut Valley. He included photographs of scaled flesh models of *Anchisaurus* (also of other side with skeleton; Figs 4J, K), the theropod dinosaur *Podokesaurus* (see Section 3.2.1), the aetosaur *Stegomus* (Upper Triassic, see Section 4.2), and the presumed maker of the ichnotaxon *Anomoepus* (probably

an ornithischian dinosaur; see Olsen & Rainforth, 2003) with one individual crouching so that the distal ischial region touches the ground.

Additional remarks on *Anchisaurus* and *Ammosaurus* were published in Huene (1914a), described as Triassic dinosaurs. The genus *Anchisaurus* included the two specimens of *Anchisaurus colurus* and *Anchisaurus solus*. The genus *Ammosaurus* included only one species, *A. major*, and the other material from Connecticut was referred to as *Thecodontosaurus polyzelus*, given to its similarity to the material of *Thecodontosaurus antiquus* in the Peabody Museum collection, currently the type material of *Asylosaurus yalensis*. In his classification scheme of Archosauria, von Huene (1914a) considered these three genera, namely *Anchisaurus*, *Ammosaurus* and *Thecodontosaurus*, as the most primitive lineage of the Order Saurischia, from which several lineages offshoot in the Jurassic. In Huene (1914b), the family Thecodontosauridae is recognized as the most primitive lineage of the Suborder Pachypodosauria von Huene, 1914a. The family Thecodontosauridae included as well *Gyposaurus capensis* Broom, 1911 from South Africa and the dubious German coelophysoid material of *Pterospondylus*. The system of Saurischia *sensu* Huene thus considered two larger groups: Coelurosauria, which included genera like *Procompsognathus* and *Saltopus*, slender, small and bipedal carnivore dinosaurs, and Pachypodosauria, which included the larger prosauropods, with *Ammosaurus* amongst its earliest members. In 1914c, the Saurischian system is described in more detail, where Thecodontosauridae is placed in a group called “Allophagi” on a path towards the Sauropoda. *Anchisaurus* is also placed in this path. On the other path, the “Therophagi,” are the carnivore-looking saurischians that are not coelurosaurian-like, and this was on a path towards the “Megalosaurids.” This path included *Zanclodon*, theropod teeth found near sauropodomorph skeletons; *Teratosaurus*, which included a rauisuchian maxilla attributed to a sauropodomorph; and *Gresslyosaurus*, a material at the time only found in Switzerland that in size was more similar to the “Therophagi”.

“Triassic Life of the Connecticut Valley” by Lull (1915) is an extremely important volume, as is the revised version (Lull, 1953), that deals with all aspects of the subject, including the history, geology, productive localities, climate, plants, invertebrate remains and trails, and the vertebrate bones and footprints. Lull (1915), who chronicled the skeletal remains from the Connecticut Valley, reproduced many of the drawings and quoted extensively from the original accounts published in English, as well as providing additional descriptions but only a few new figures. He did not utilize or refer to any of the excellent photographs of the YPM specimens in Huene (1906) or his own drawings (Figs 4N, O) of *Ammosaurus major* in Huene (1907-1908). There is

also no reference to the later papers of Huene (1914a-d), probably because reprints were received too late to be considered (C. Schuchert's copy of 1914d in YPM VP library, the first to be published, is stamped "Jul. 1 1914"). He used photographs of his scaled models from Lull (1912), including the flesh and skeletal sides of the model of *Anchisaurus colurus* (Lull, 1915, pls IV, X; only former in Lull 1953, pl. IV) (Figs 4J, K). Lull (1915) pointed out that the type species of *Anchisaurus* Marsh, 1885 must be *Megadactylus polyzelus* Hitchcock, 1865 (as noted by Marsh 1889) and he disagreed with the arguments of Huene (1906) for referring it to *Thecodontosaurus*. However, he noted that, if Huene were correct, then *Anchisaurus* would be a subjective junior synonym of *Thecodontosaurus*, and this would leave the other two species, *Anchisaurus colurus* Marsh, 1892 and *A. solus* Marsh, 1892, without a generic name. Von Huene (1920a) considered that Marsh's Theropoda did not account for the Sauropoda, which had affinities with *Plateosaurus* and *Anchisaurus*, and proposed to replace it with its system of Coelurosauria and Pachypodosauria. Within the Pachypodosauria, von Huene recognized several species that had a carnivore diet and questioned whether Pachypodosauria and Coelurosauria had a common ancestor in the way the name Theropoda suggested. One of the lineages of Pachypodosauria included slender gracile animals that von Huene considered carnivores, such as *Palaeosaurus*, *Zanclodon*, *Teratosaurus* and *Gresslyosaurus*. The diet of these animals was mostly inferred from *Teratosaurus* and *Zanclodon* (Regalado Fernandez *et al.*, 2023). Accordingly, von Huene (1920a) suggested that this lineage of carnivorous pachypodosaurians could be part of Coelurosauria, and erected the name Carnosauria for this scenario. Likewise, the rest of the Pachypodosauria that included omnivore and herbivore animals, such as *Anchisaurus*, *Thecodontosaurus* and *Plateosaurus*, that shared features with the Sauropoda, was separated into the Prosauropoda. This scheme would later become the Sauropodomorpha (von Huene, 1932). Huene (1932) reviewed the Connecticut Valley prosauropods, providing short descriptions and measurements of the bones. In response to the comments by Lull (1915), he made *Anchisaurus colurus* the type species of *Yaleosaurus* Huene, 1932 as *Y. colurus* (Marsh, 1891) (with a skeletal reconstruction, Huene, 1932, pl. 54, fig. 3). He also referred *Anchisaurus solus* to *Ammosaurus* as *A. solus* (with a skeletal reconstruction, Huene, 1932, pl. 49, fig. 1, 1956, fig. 497 as *A. major*). Huene (1932) argued that *Ammosaurus* was not an herbivorous prosauropod but a carnivorous dinosaur, with the Ammosauridae as a primitive lineage of the Coelurosauria as per Huene (1914b, c, 1956). This was based mostly on the characters of YPM VP 209 (Figs 7, 9G, H), viz., large skull (juvenile character), reduced presacral vertebral count of 23 (actually 25), amazingly slender vertebrae

(but those of YPM VP 1883 are similar), tibia almost certainly longer than femur (almost certainly the reverse, femur up to 110 mm versus 82 mm), hollowness of the long bones (also true for YPM VP 1883), and form of the ilium with long anterior process (in YPM VP 208, 209 but also 1883; Figs 12A, F-H).

Within the suborder Theropoda, Romer (1945: 598-599) included the Ammosauridae in the infraorder Coelurosauria and the Prosauropoda (including *Yaleosaurus*) as an infraorder separate from the suborder Sauropoda. Lull (1953), who updated and made minor revisions to the sections on the skeletal remains in his 1915 paper, classified *Ammosaurus* as an early coelurosaurian dinosaur and *Yaleosaurus* as a valid genus of theropod. Huene (1956, fig. 497) reused his 1932 skeletal reconstruction of the primitive coelurosaurian theropod *Ammosaurus solus* for *A. major*. For the prosauropod sauropodomorph *Yaleosaurus*, Huene (1956, fig. 522) enlarged the skull figure from that on the skeletal reconstruction in Huene (1932, pl. 54, fig. 3).

3.1.4. Studies in the 1960s and 1970s

Colbert (1963, 1970) briefly reviewed the fossil bones and footprints from the Connecticut Valley. Colbert (1964a, 1970) followed Huene (1932, 1956) in regarding *Ammosaurus* as a Triassic carnivorous dinosaur that, along with the Palaeosauridae and Teratosauridae, were placed in the Palaeosauria (=Teratosauria). Charig *et al.* (1965) resurrected the Prosauropoda and Sauropodomorpha of Huene (1920a, 1932). However, because the postcranial bones of Colbert's "Triassic carnivores" were not definitely associated with the cranial bones bearing carnivorous teeth (i.e., teeth that are conical, slightly recurved, oval in cross-section, with fine serrations), they referred the former to the Prosauropoda within the Sauropodomorpha, not the Theropoda, as did Walker (1964). However, Charig *et al.* (1965: 213) noted that *Ammosaurus* did not seem to fit satisfactorily into any of the existing categories of saurischian dinosaurs. Romer (1966: 369) placed the Prosauropoda within the Sauropodomorpha, with *Ammosaurus* as Theropoda *incertae sedis*.

Galton (1971) concluded that *Ammosaurus solus* represents a juvenile individual of *A. major* and based on the characters of specimens YPM VP 208 and 209, showed that *Ammosaurus* is a prosauropod that was referred to the Anchisauridae, along with the other prosauropod genera except those referred to the Melanosauridae (see Galton, 1985). The skull and pes of *Anchisaurus* (YPM VP 1883) and the pelvic girdle of *Ammosaurus* (YPM VP 208) were figured by Bakker & Galton (1974) for comparisons in their paper in which the Saurischia and Ornithischia were reunited, together with birds, in the class Dinosauria. This "new" class was united by a

suite of morphological features related to upright stance, bipedality, and an inferred metabolic level above that of typical reptiles. The Dinosauria is now accepted as a monophyletic category within the class Reptilia (e.g., Gauthier, 1986; Benton, 1990; Sereno, 1998, 1999; Paul, 2016; Baron *et al.*, 2017).

Galton (1976) provided a detailed description of all the early sauropodomorph specimens from the Connecticut Valley and discussed the characters used by Huene and Lull. He recognized two taxa, *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (including *A. colurus*) and *Ammosaurus major* (including *A. solus*), within the “prosauropod” family Anchisauridae that was reviewed by Galton & Cluver (1976). The late William (Bill) Amaral (MCZ) in 1977 undertook careful additional preparation on the skull of YPM VP 1883 (cf. Huene, 1906, pl. 1, figs 1, 2 and Galton, 1976, figs 13A-C with Figs 8, 9A-F; Fedak & Galton, 2007, figs 1, 3, 4). Reconstructions in lateral and ventral views of the braincase of *Anchisaurus colurus* (YPM VP 1883) were published by Galton & Bakker (1985, figs 4C, D). Carroll (1988: 621) listed *Ammosaurus* and *Anchisaurus* in the Plateosauria (=Prosauropoda) within the Sauropodomorpha.

3.1.5. Studies in the 2000s

In the cladistic analysis of Galton & Upchurch (2004; also, Upchurch *et al.*, 2007), *Anchisaurus* and *Ammosaurus* are sister taxa within the Anchisauridae. Anchisauria Galton & Upchurch, 2004 was erected for the most recent common ancestor of *Anchisaurus* and *Melanorosaurus* (see Galton *et al.*, 2005; Yates, 2007) and all its descendants (Fig. 1B). Based on a reanalysis of the characters of *Anchisaurus*, Yates (2004) showed that *Anchisaurus* was potentially one of the first and smallest sauropod dinosaurs. This resulted from the definition of Sauropoda given by Sereno (1998: 63), viz., “all sauropodomorphs more closely related to the sauropod *Saltasaurus* than to the prosauropod *Plateosaurus*.” However, this definition overlooked the possibility that traditional prosauropods do not form a natural group, but instead are a highly pectinate or comb-like array on the stem of the Sauropoda (Fig. 1B). Consequently, because of the relatively basal position of *Plateosaurus*, this definition includes most traditional non-sauropod sauropodomorphs. Yates (2007: 32; 2010) favored a modified definition of Sauropoda that, by replacing *Plateosaurus engelhardti* (now *P. trossingensis*: ICZN, 2019; Galton, 2012c) with the near-sauropod *Melanosaurus readi* (Upper Triassic, South Africa) as the exclusive anchor taxon, better conforms to the traditional concept of the group. *Anchisaurus* is basal to the near-sauropod *Melanorosaurus* (see Galton *et al.*, 2005; Yates, 2007) but closer to Sauropoda than the “core prosauropods” *Plateosaurus* (see Huene, 1926)

and *Massospondylus* (see Chapelle & Choiniere, 2018; Barrett *et al.*, 2019) (Fig. 1B).

The braincase of *Anchisaurus* (YPM VP 1883) has long been characterized anteroventrally as having a pair of unusually short basiptyergoid processes (Figs 4F, 10E). However, based on a study of the skull block, Fedak (2003, 2005) suggested in abstracts that a piece of matrix, which included most of the antero-ventral basisphenoid-parasphenoid complex, was lost sometime in the 1890s during collection or early preparation, an absence that remained unrecognized for 120 years. He argued that the missing processes were originally of normal proportions in YPM VP 1883 (Figs 10F, G), as in the ventral part of the braincase of the skull of YPM VP 209 that he carefully prepared (Fig. 9H). Fedak & Galton (2007) document the evidence for this loss and for the preservational distortions of the skull of YPM VP 1883 (see Figs 8, 9E, F). They re-described this skull, along with the cranial fragments of YPM VP 209 (Figs 9G, H), and reviewed some of the sauropod-like characters of the *Anchisaurus* skull.

Sereno (2007) suggested that *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865) is a *nomen dubium* because its holotype (AMC 41104; Figs 2, 3, 4A-C) lacks any diagnostic characters. He saw no merits in trying to conserve *Anchisaurus* over *Ammosaurus* so YPM VP 208, 209 and 1883 were all referred to *Ammosaurus major* (Marsh, 1889). This was a follow up to Sereno (1999, ESM: 14) who listed “*Ammosaurus* (=Anchisaurus)” without giving any reasons to support this synonymy.

McDonald (2010, fig. 5-18) illustrated a partial pes consisting of the distal parts of metatarsals 1 to 4 with the associated phalanges. It was found in a loose redstone boulder in a gravel pit in Ellington, Conn., a few miles east of East Windsor (map locality 30, Lull, 1953: 68). He identified it as *Anchisaurus*. Still, this partial right pes exposed in anterior (dorsal) view is more correctly identified as early Sauropodomorpha indet.

Yates (2010) suggested a few unique characters or autapomorphies for AMC 41104 and YPM VP 1883 that supported the referral of *Ammosaurus major* to *Anchisaurus polyzelus*, but these characters were also not diagnostic (Galton, 2012a, b). All the autapomorphies suggested for *A. polyzelus* are based on YPM VP 1883, which has been the basis for the characters of *Anchisaurus* since Marsh (1892, 1893, 1896a). In addition, Anchisauridae Marsh, 1885 is the oldest family of early sauropodomorphs and Anchisauria Galton & Upchurch, 2004 is the least inclusive clade containing *Anchisaurus* and *Melanorosaurus* (Fig. 1B; Upchurch *et al.*, 2007; Yates, 2007, 2010). A petition by Galton (2012a; but see Demirjian, 2012; reply, Galton, 2012b) was accepted by the ICZN (2015) to designate YPM VP 1883 as the neotype (replacing the non-diagnostic AMC 41104) for *Megadactylus polyzelus* Hitchcock, 1865, the type species of *Anchisaurus* Marsh, 1885.

Several morphological characteristics in AMC 41104,

such as the shape of the vertebrae, interpreted as either posterior dorsals or sacral vertebrae, the slender metacarpals, metatarsals and phalanges, and possibly the tibia and fibula having a similar length (Galton, 1976), indicate affinities of this material to early diverging sauropodomorphs such as *Efraasia* and *Asylosaurus*, explaining the confusing literature of the first half of the 20th century where *Anchisaurus* and *Ammosaurus* were interpreted as either primitive “pachypodosaurians” related to *Thecodontosaurus*, or more derived ones related to Sauropoda. Further analyses with techniques like the digital assembly of μ CT scanning to code morphological character in phylogenetic analyses may better reveal the relationships of AMC 41104 among the “prosauropods”. AMC 41104 would be the second representative of a ghost lineage of *Efraasia*-like sauropodomorphs surviving the Triassic-Jurassic boundary, with the first one potentially being *Arcusaurus* from the Upper Elliot Formation of South Africa (Yates *et al.*, 2011).

3.1.6. Supposed character differences for *Anchisaurus* and *Ammosaurus*

The validity of most of the characters used by Galton (1976, 1990; also, Galton & Upchurch, 2004; Upchurch

et al., 2007) to separate *Ammosaurus* Marsh, 1891 (based on the larger individual YPM VP 208) from *Anchisaurus* Marsh, 1885 (based on the medium-sized individual YPM VP 1883) have been questioned. Some are regarded as the result of the size difference, as for the broader pes of *Ammosaurus* (Figs 11R, S; Cooper, 1981; Yates, 2004), or the differences are not supported by measurements of the metatarsal widths (MT, Figs 11R, S; Yates, 2004) and for the proportional smaller pedal first claw or ungual of *Anchisaurus* (Figs 11R-T; Yates, 2010). Other differences are regarded as the result of postmortem factors of preservation. Thus crushing would account for the broader metatarsus/pes of *Ammosaurus* (dorso-ventrally crushed, Figs 4L, O, 5B, C, 11S, 14C-F; Sereno, 2007), but the pes of *Anchisaurus* is also similarly crushed (Figs 6A-C, 14A), and for the longer distal lateral recess for the fibula on the tibia of *Ammosaurus* (anteroposteriorly crushed, *, Figs 4O, 5B, C, 11U) versus the proximo-distal crushing in *Anchisaurus* (*, Figs 11O-Q; Yates, 2004). Preservation loss of the thin marginal bone supposedly resulted in modification of the form of the proximal ends of the lower hip bones, the pubis and ischium (Figs 12A, B, G). Emargination also supposedly resulted in a large obturator opening for the pubis of *Anchisaurus* (Figs 12G, I-N) compared to the closed obturator foramen of *Ammosaurus* (Figs 12A-D;

Fig. 8. Basal sauropodomorph dinosaur *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865) from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn. YPM VP 1883, neotype; holotype of *A. colurus* Marsh, 1891. Figures of skull to show location of the portion missing since 1884 and post-depositional distortions. A-C: photographs (A-C) and interpretative line drawings (A'-C') of the skull in occipital (A), right lateral (B) and oblique left lateral views (C) [for stereo photographs of skull prior to further preparation see Galton (1976, figs 13A-C)]. Explanations for missing piece and distortions in A-C (from Fedak & Galton, 2007): A, the missing ventral portion of the left quadrate (arrowhead) is truncated by the missing piece of the skull block. The right paroccipital process and posterior portion of the right side of braincase (two arrows) were fractured prior to preservation. B, the deformation to the right side of the skull exposes the medial surface of the braincase (**), and a fragment of the paroccipital process (not shown, location marked with *) were preserved at the ventral tip of the right squamosal. The white arrows demarcate the repaired oblique crack in the skull block (see B, Fig. 9E), and the missing area of the left quadrate and basisphenoid (Fig. 9F), which represents the posterior edge of the missing portion of the skull block. C, white arrows demarcate the missing piece, and the posterior end of the maxilla is disarticulated from its contact (*) with the jugal. D, photograph and line drawing (D') of the posterior dorsal region of skull. The parietal-frontal contact has been lost on the left side, but the open sutural contact remains visible on the right. The postorbitals are displaced posteromedially from their sutural contacts with the frontals (*); the postorbitals did not contact the parietals, and the supratemporal fossa on the frontal remains visible, particularly on the right side. The gap between the parietals and supraoccipital is a consequence of deformation and displacement of the braincase. The white surface on the ventral end of the right frontal is a broken surface for the missing rounded slightly expanded tip that was present until the early 2000s [cf. Figs 4D, E, 9A as *; Galton (1976, fig. 11A)]. Broken bone surfaces are identified with diagonal lines and matrix and irrelevant elements are shaded grey. Abbreviations as listed below for Figures 8 to 10 with the addition of prefixes for left (l) and right (r) sides. Photos A-D by PMG, E-H modified from Fedak & Galton (2007); scale bars = 10 mm (A-F) and 20 mm (G-H).

Abbreviations for Figs 8-10: an, angular; aof, antorbital fossa; ar, articular; asaf, anterior surangular foramen; bo, Bs, basioccipital; bp, Bpt, basiptyergoid process; bs, basisphenoid; ca, carotid artery foramen; cc, cavum cochlear; ci, crista interfenestra; Col, columella or stapes; cp, crista prootica; cs, crista sellaris; d, dentary; ect, ectopterygoid; emf, external mandibular fenestra; f, frontal; fj, foramen jugularis; flp, foramen lacerum posterior; fm, Fm, foramen magnum; fo, fenestra ovalis; j, jugal; l, lachrymal; ltf, lower temporal fenestra; lw, lateral walls of sella turcica; mf, metotic fissure; mx, maxilla; oc, occipital condyle; op, Op, opisthotic; p, parietal; pm, premaxilla; po, postorbital; pop, pp, paroccipital process; ppf, posttemporal foramen; pr, prootic; prf, prefrontal; ps, Ps, parasphenoid rostrum; psaf, posterior surangular foramen; pt, Pt, pterygoid; q, quadrate; qj, quadratojugal; sa, surangular; snf, subnarial foramen; so, So, supraoccipital; sq, squamosal; Tub, basal tubera; utf, upper temporal fenestra; vc, vidian canal for internal carotid artery; V, VII and XII, foramina for cranial nerves. Scale line = 20 mm.

Yates, 2004). A similar loss resulted in the emarginated obturator plate of the ischium of *Ammosaurus*, so the subacetabular region is shallow with the formation of an “obturator process” (Fig. 12A, B; Sereno, 2007; Yates, 2010). However, only the proximal part of the ischium is preserved in YPM VP 1883 (Fig. 12G). A result of the questioning of the validity of these suggested character differences is that *Ammosaurus* is now generally regarded as a subjective junior synonym of *Anchisaurus*.

3.1.7. Autapomorphies suggested for *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (YPM VP 209, 1883)

From the work of Galton (1976, 1990), Galton & Upchurch (2004), Cooper (1980), Yates (2004, 2010) and Sereno (2007), the suggested autapomorphies based on YPM VP 209 and 1883 are:

1. Transversally expanded ventral or lower process of the postorbital (Yates, 2004, fig. 8). This character is present in the adult specimen YPM VP 1883 (po, Figs 8C, 10B; * Fig. 9C), and in the juvenile YPM VP 209 (Fabbri *et al.*, 2021, fig. 1), being a valid autapomorphy; it is developed convergently in Eusauropoda.
2. A pit on the outer surface of the quadrate, just above the articular condyle (Yates, 2004, fig. 4, 2010, fig. 1A), is a valid autapomorphy that is only present in YPM VP 1883 (q, Fig. 10B; * Fig. 9D).
3. Slender and funnel-shaped first (dorsosacral) sacral rib with a base occupying less than half of the length of the first sacral centrum (Figs 4M, 5F, 13G, H, J-L; Yates, 2010, 33% and 42% in YPM VP 1883 and 209). However, this character is also present in the Argentinian lower Jurassic sauropodomorph *Leoneosaurus taquetrensis* (Pol *et al.*, 2011, fig. 8; plots as a sister taxon to *Anchisaurus* within the Massopoda in cladogram of Apaldetti *et al.*, 2021), so it is not a valid autapomorphy.
4. Posterior dorsal centra approximately twice as long as the height of the face for the adjacent centrum (Figs 6C, F, G, 13E, for YPM VP 1883; only visible for sacral vertebrae in YPM VP 208, Fig. 5G). This autapomorphy was suggested by Sereno (2007), and as discussed by Yates (2010), it is not a function of the small size of YPM VP 209 and 1883.
5. A foramen or depression opening ventrally on the base of the second sacral rib (Yates, 2004: 7, fig. 1). Originally, it was illustrated as a foramen (Fig. 4M; see Figs 13J-M for YPM VP 209). However, Sereno (2007) pointed out that it has not been demonstrated to penetrate deeply into the cortex of the bone but appears to be developed as a shallow depression (i.e., for YPM VP 208). Nevertheless, Yates (2010) notes that the feature remains distinctive, and it stands as a valid autapomorphy that is visible in YPM VP 209 and 1883. However, the “foramen” in the area labelled “F” in YPM VP 1883 by Yates (2004, fig. 1A; 2010, fig. 3B as “o, opening of foramen or pit”; Fig. 13G, *) consists of three very small foramina arranged in a vertical row. Consequently, this character is not a valid autapomorphy for *Anchisaurus*. The shape of this sacral rib is also different in YPM VP 1883 (Figs 13G-I) and 208 (Figs 13J-M). However, the shallow depression on the second sacral rib in YPM VP 208 and the vertical row of three very small foramina in YPM VP 1883 are valid autapomorphies for *Ammosaurus* and *Anchisaurus*, respectively.
6. A long, narrow preacetabular lobe or anterior process of the ilium, that is at least twice as long as it is high at its base, is observable in YPM VP 1883 and 208 (Figs 12A, B, F-H). It should be noted that this lobe is proportionally longer in YPM VP 208 but this is probably a function of the smaller size of YPM VP 1883. However, this lobe is also elongate in *Leoneosaurus taquetrensis* (Pol *et al.*, 2011, fig. 11; see character 3). This is also the case in two specimens from the Lower Jurassic of South Africa, NMQR 3314, previously referred to *Melanorosaurus* but currently thought of as a yet-to-be-described sauropodomorph

Fig. 9. A-F: Basal sauropodomorph dinosaur *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865) from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn. YPM VP 1883, neotype; holotype of *A. colurus* Marsh, 1891, details of skull: A, right temporal region in dorsolateral view (cf. Fig. 8D) to show rounded ventral tip of frontal (*) that has been missing since early 2000s; shown by Marsh (1892, 1896a; see Fig. 4C) and Galton (1976, figs 13A, A') but not by Fedak & Galton (2007; see Fig. 8D) and Yates (2010; see Fig. 10B). B-C: left postorbital bar in posterolateral (B) and posterior views (C) (cf. Yates, 2004, figs 8A, B) to show transversely expanded sutural surface of ventral ramus of postorbital (*) for jugal, an autapomorphy for *Anchisaurus*. D, right mandibular articular region to show distal pit or depression on quadrate (*), an autapomorphy for *Anchisaurus*. E-F: photographs and explanatory line drawings (E', F') of the braincase in left ventrolateral (E) and right ventrolateral (F) views. The white arrows demarcate the repaired oblique crack in the skull block (E, F), and the missing area of the left quadrate and basisphenoid (F), which represents the posterior edge of the missing portion of the skull block (see Fig. 8). G-H: small individual YPM 209 (holotype of *Anchisaurus solus* Marsh, 1892), long-wave UV light photographs and explanatory line drawings (G', H') in left dorsolateral (G) and right ventrolateral (H) views. Anterior is toward the bottom left (G) or bottom right (H). The black arrow (G) identifies the boundary between the right postorbital ventral process and right jugal, whereas the arrowhead identifies the location of the dentary tooth examined with SEM by Fedak & Galton (2007, fig. 7). Broken bone surfaces are identified with diagonal lines, matrix and irrelevant elements are shaded grey; see caption to Fig. 8 for abbreviations; photographs A-D taken by PMG, E-H modified from Fedak & Galton (2007); scale bars = 10 mm (A-F) and 20 mm (G, H). ▶

(McPhee *et al.*, 2017), and in SAM 990 that probably represents a juvenile individual of *Massospondylus contra* Galton & Cluver (1976), so the long anterior process is not a valid autapomorphy. It is convergent in the sauropod *Kotasaurus yamanpalliensis* (Lower Jurassic, India; Yadagiri, 2001).

7. Dorsoventrally flattened ischial blades set at a low angle to each other (Yates, 2010, fig. 2). For YPM VP 208 this flattening is probably a function of the dorsoventral crushing of the ischia (Fig. 5B). Only the proximal part of the ischium is preserved in YPM VP 1883 (Figs 6A, B, 12G). However, this character

Fig. 10. Basal sauropodomorph dinosaur *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1856) from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn., YPM VP 1883, neotype, holotype of *A. colurus* Marsh, 1891. A, reconstruction of skeleton in left lateral view (note that only proximal end of ischium is present, Fig. 12G, animal body length ~1.6 m, humerus length 150 mm). B-C: reconstruction of skull in left lateral (B) and dorsal (C) views. D-E: braincase as preserved in occipital (D) and ventral (E) views. Note stapes (Col) that is shown in stereo photographs of skull in Galton (1976, figs 13B, C) is no longer present (Figs 8A, 9E; Yates, 2004, fig. 3A). F-G: restoration of braincase of YPM VP 1883 in left lateral (F) and occipital (G) views with shaded parts restored from skull of small individual (YPM VP 209). A, kindly provided by G. Paul (Baltimore), who retains the copyright; B-C modified from Yates (2010), D-E modified from Huene (1914a), F-G modified from Fedak & Galton (2007), for abbreviations, see caption to Fig. 8; scale bars = 25 mm (B, C) and 10 mm (D-G).

is also present in the massopod sauropodomorph *Leonerasaurus taquetrensis* (Pol *et al.*, 2011, fig. 12; Apaldetti *et al.*, 2021, fig. 3) so it is not a valid autoapomorphy. The uncrushed distal portions of the ischia of AMC 41104 are not dorsoventrally flattened and are set at a low angle to each other (Figs 2J-L, 3M-O, 4C), resembling those of the early sauropodomorph *Asylosaurus yalensis* (Galton, 2007; Upper Triassic, England).

8. Pubis with open obturator notch and a reduced triangular-shaped articular surface for the ischium (Figs 12G, I-N). Yates (2010: 3) noted that, as “discussed by Yates (2004: 3) and agreed upon by Sereno (2007), the obturator notch of the pubis of YPM VP 1883 could easily be the result of post-depositional loss of the thin bone that forms the posteroventral margin of the obturator foramen and is not a reliable character to separate the two taxa.”

Fig. 11. Appendicular bones of early sauropodomorph dinosaurs from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn. A-R: YPM VP 1883, neotype of *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865), holotype of *A. colurus* Marsh, 1891. A-B: left scapula and coracoid (A) and right scapula (B) in A, lateral and B, posterior views; C-H: right humerus in C, lateral and D-E, anterior views; F-H: distal part in F, anterior; G, distal and H, posterior views. Yates (2004: 14, fig. 18) cites the loss of a well-defined fossa on distal flexor surface (see E, F) as a sauropod synapomorphy, but this is probably due to antero-posterior crushing (see G); I, right radius, ulna and manus in lateral view (for stereo photograph of bones, see Galton, 1976); J-L: distal phalanges of manus in medial view of digits: J, 1; K, 2 and L, 3; M, right femur in anterior view; N-Q: right tibia and fibula in N, lateral and O-P, posterior view with Q, posterolateral view of distal tibia, fibula, astragalus and calcaneum; R, right pes in ventral view. S-U: YPM 208, holotype of *Ammosaurus major* (Marsh, 1889), S, left pes in dorsal view; T, phalanges of digit 1 in lateral view and U, distal left tibia in anterior view. For photographs and extra views see Galton (1976). A-D, I-O, R-U modified from Galton (1976); photographs E-H, P, Q taken by PMG. Abbreviation: * recess for fibula; A, astragalus; C, calcaneum; CO, coracoid; d cr, deltopectoral crest; DT, distal tarsal, F, fibula; FE, femur; gl, glenoid; les, lesser trochanter; MT, metatarsal; oc, outer condyle; S, scapula; T, tibia; V, vertebral centrum; 1-5, digits 1 to 5; scale bars = 50 mm (A-T) and 10 mm (U).

Fig. 12. A-N: pelvic girdles of early sauropodomorph dinosaurs from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn. A-F: YPM VP 208, holotype of *Ammosaurus major* (Marsh, 1889), A-B: reconstructed girdle in A, left lateral and B, ventral views; C-E: left proximal pubis and ischium (C-D) to show posterior part of obturator foramen of pubis (white line) and broken ventral edge of ischium (white dotted line) with newly prepared bone (*) beyond it as in E; F: right ilium in lateral view. G-N: YPM 1883, neotype of *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865) and holotype of *A. colurus* Marsh, 1891. G, reconstruction of girdle in right lateral view; H, right ilium in lateral view; I-L: right pubis: I, complete bone in posterior view [cf. Yates (2004, fig. 11); stereo photograph in Galton (1976, fig. 12)] and J, proximal part in posterior and slightly lateral view; K, sutural surface for ischium in ventral and slightly lateral view and L, proximal part in ventro-medial view. M, right pubis in lateral view and N, pubes in postero-ventral view. O-P: early sauropodomorph *Efraasia minor* (Huene, 1907-08) [Galton (1973, figs 11A-D as *E. diagnostica*), see taxonomic review by Yates (2003)] from Upper Triassic of Germany: O, pubes in postero-ventral view and P, right pubis in lateral view. A, B, G, M-P modified from Galton (1976), photographs C-F, H-L taken by PMG. Abbreviations: * in A, C-E, emarginated border of ischium (as -----), the result of incomplete preparation; * in G, I, J, L-N, pubis with open obturator foramen and triangular sutural surface for ischium, an autapomorphy for *Anchisaurus*. a, acetabulum; ap, anterior process; is, surface for ischium; ob, obturator opening; obt p, obturator process; p, pubic process; scale bars = 25 mm (A-I, L), 20 mm (J), 10 mm (K) and 50 mm (M-P).

The missing bone was restored by Huene (1914a, fig. 10). However, the “open obturator foramen” for YPM VP 1883 would also involve the loss of some of the thicker posteroventral part of the sutural region for the ischium (see Fig. 12A-D, O, P cf. 12G, I-N for comparative thicknesses of this end). This region in YPM VP 1883 (Figs 12I-N) is proportionally small with a triangular ischial articular surface. The medial and lateral surfaces of this region are smooth and taper to end in a sharp edge (Figs 12I-N; Galton, 1976, figs 19, 20A, B; Yates, 2004, fig. 11), not a thick eroded edge. In YPM VP 208 (Figs 12A-D), as in *Efrassia* (Figs 12O, P), *Plateosaurus* (Huene, 1926) and other early sauropodomorphs, the ischial sutural area is thick with a closed obturator foramen, the plesiomorphic condition. The differences in these pubes (Figs 12A-D, G, I-N) indicate that *Ammosaurus major* (Marsh, 1889), based on YPM VP 208, is not a subjective junior synonym of *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865), based on the neotype YPM VP 1883.

3.1.8. Autapomorphies for neotype of *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (YPM VP 1883)

1. Transversally expanded ventral or lower process of the postorbital (Yates, 2004; *, Figs 9B, C).
2. A pit on the outer surface of the quadrate, just above the articular condyle (Yates, 2004; *, Fig. 9D).
3. Ventral surface of base of sacral rib 2 has a vertical row of three very small foramina (*, Figs 13G, I).
4. Pubis with open obturator notch and a reduced triangular shaped articular surface for the ischium (* Figs 12G, I-N; Galton, 1976).

3.1.9. Characters of *Ammosaurus major*

1. A ventral depression on the base of the second sacral rib (Yates, 2004: 7, fig. 1) is a valid autapomorphy (Fig. 4M, *, Figs 13J-M; for discussion, see Section 3.1.7, character 5).
2. Large fenestra piercing the third sacral rib (second primordial sacral) (Fig. 4M, **, Figs 13J-L, N-P). This character was listed by Yates (2004: 7, fig. 1) as an autapomorphy for *Anchisaurus polyzelus*, but as this region is only preserved in YPM VP 208, it is a possible autapomorphy for *Ammosaurus major*. However, Yates (2010: 739) noted that this character must be regarded as uncertain because it could be due to the postmortem loss of bone from this thin, delicate area. The rib of the last sacral vertebra of the sauropod *Brontosaurus excelsus* (genus valid, Tschopp *et al.*, 2015; YPM VP 1980, Marsh, 1896a, pl. 23; Ostrom & McIntosh, 1999, pl. 27) has two distally diverging

thicker parts that are in the same horizontal plane, and the adjacent edges are irregular with most of the thin bone missing in between. However, in YPM VP 208, the edge bordering the opening was originally mostly smooth (Huene, 1906, pl. 6 for photograph that it is rotated 180 degrees), as indicated by Marsh (1892, 1896a) (Fig. 4M), although now part of the sacral rib (anterior bar) is missing (**, Figs 13J-L, N-P). The sacral rib is oriented slightly ventrolaterally, and the transverse process (posterior bar) has a higher origin and is oriented slightly dorsolaterally (Figs 13O, P). These processes diverge distally (Figs 13K, L, O, P; see stereo photograph in Galton, 1976, fig. 25A) and are not in the same plane, as incorrectly indicated by Yates (2004, fig. 1B; Fig. 13J cf. Figs 4J, 13K, L, N-P), and the “fenestra” or opening (***) is not within the sacral rib. This character is unknown in any other early sauropodomorph and is the second autapomorphy for *Ammosaurus*: No connection beyond the bases of the transverse process and sacral rib of the third sacral vertebra (second primordial sacral) (modified from Galton, 1976: 82).

3. Yates (2004: 7) listed a “ventrally emarginated obturator plate of ischium”, so the subacetabular region is shallow with the formation of an “obturator process” (Figs 5D, 12A, B), as an autapomorphy of *Anchisaurus polyzelus*. This region is not preserved in YPM VP 1883, so this character relates only to *Ammosaurus major*. Yates (2010: 3) agreed with Sereno (2007) that this ventral emargination “may well be another artefact of postdepositional damage.” This irregular edge (Figs 12C-E) is not natural and further preparation by Marilyn Fox (YPM VP) uncovered additional bone beyond it (Figs 12D, E; ---, *). This emargination is an artifact of preparation, as only recognized by R. S. Lull in Huene (1907-1908, fig. 298; see Fig. 4N), so the anteroventral shape of the ischium is unknown.
4. Yates (2004: 6) noted that the manus of YPM VP 2125 (Figs 1F-G) from East Windsor has a plateosaurian synapomorphy, “the presence of an enlarged distal carpal 1 [...], a character apparently not present in *Anchisaurus polyzelus*” (Fig. 6N; also Fig. 4A for AMC 41004). Sereno (2007: 280) noted that Galton (1976, fig. 32) incorrectly drew carpals 1 and 2 as a single element for YPM VP 1883 (Fig. 11I). Huene (1914a, fig. 9) illustrated and drew attention to the two distal carpals in this manus (Fig. 6N). Yates (2010: 735) subsequently noted that “the strongly hatchet-shaped form of the deltopectoral crest (of the humerus), the large distal carpal bone and the great proximal width of metacarpal one relative to the other metacarpals all suggest that this specimen is not the same species as those from Manchester” (Figs 1F-H cf. Figs 6H, I, N, 11C-E, I). Yates (2010) only recognized one taxon from Manchester,

Fig. 13. Vertebrae of early sauropodomorph dinosaurs from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn. A-I: YPM VP 1883, neotype of *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865), holotype of *A. colurus* Marsh, 1891 in left lateral (A-E), and ventral (F-I) views. A, neural arch of atlas; B, axis; C, cervical vertebra 3; D, dorsal vertebra 2; E-F, dorsal vertebra 10, * in E for low dorsal centrum, a synapomorphy for Anchisauridae (*Anchisaurus* + *Ammosaurus*); G-H: dorsosacral and sacral 1 (sacral vertebrae 1 and 2) with ribs as preserved (G) and restored (H); I, right sacral rib 1 (of primordial sacral vertebra 1) with * in G and I for position of three very small foramina arranged in a vertical row, an autapomorphy for *Anchisaurus*. J-P: YPM VP 208, holotype of *Ammosaurus major* (Marsh, 1889), sacrum in J-L: ventral view (for K see stereo photograph in Galton, 1976, fig. 25A), L, restoration with right ilium; M, sacral vertebra 2 (primordial sacral 1) with rib as preserved in ventral view. N-P: sacral vertebra 3 (primordial sacral 2) in N, ventral and slightly posterior; O, postero-latero-ventral and P, posterior views, * in J, L, M indicates a depression on sacral rib and ** in J, L, N-P indicates separation of primordial sacral rib 2 and the transverse process (intracostal fenestra of Yates, 2004); both characters are autapomorphies for *Ammosaurus*. A-F, H, L modified from Galton (1976), G, J modified from Yates (2004), and photographs for K, M-P taken by PMG. Abbreviations: ds, dorsosacral (first sacral) vertebra, f, position of foramen of Yates (2004); ifen, intracostal fenestra of Adam (2004); s1, first primordial sacral vertebra; s2, second primordial sacral vertebra; sr, sacral rib; tp, transverse process of sacral vertebra 2 (sacral rib 2 of Yates, 2004); scale bars = 25 mm (A-H, J-P) and 10 mm (I).

Anchisaurus polyzelus, and the manus is only known for YPM VP 1883 (Figs 6I-N, 11I), the neotype of *Anchisaurus polyzelus*. With the recognition of *Ammosaurus major* as a second valid taxon from Manchester, it is reasonable to tentatively refer to this specifically indeterminate specimen YPM VP 2125 as *Ammosaurus* cf. *A. major*.

3.1.10. Other early sauropodomorphs from the Lower Jurassic of North America

Galton (1971, 1976) described two partial skeletons from the Navajo Sandstone (Hettangian) of Arizona as *Ammosaurus? major*. However, Yates (2004) demonstrated that neither skeleton showed any synapomorphies of *Anchisaurus* (= *Ammosaurus*). He determined that MNA V744-745 (formerly MNA G2 7233) represents an indeterminate early sauropodomorph and UCMP 82961 is a sauropodomorph with a possible relationship to *Massospondylus* (Lower Jurassic, southern Africa; Chapelle & Choiniere, 2018; Barrett *et al.*, 2019). The characters used to determine these identifications are summarized by Irmis (2005, figs 3, 4), who re-illustrated the specimens. A partial skeleton from the Navajo Sandstone of southern Utah, that represents an early sauropodomorph related to plateosaurid or massospondylid sauropodomorphs, was described as *Seitaard ruessi* Sertich & Loewen, 2010 (Fig. 1B).

Olsen & Gore (1989) and Shubin *et al.* (1994) referred to undescribed bones from the McCoy Brook Formation (Hettangian) of Nova Scotia, Canada, as cf. *Ammosaurus* sp. However, these and additional undescribed partial skeletons, which now make this the most productive dinosaur locality in eastern North America (details in Sues & Olsen, 2015), show that the early sauropodomorph represented may be distinct from *Ammosaurus* (Fedak, 2006a, b; cited as “*Fendusaurus eldoni*” by Weems, 2019).

A fairly complete skeleton of an early sauropodomorph from the Kayenta Formation (Sinemurian-Pliensbachian) of northern Arizona was named *Sarhsaurus aurifrontalis* Rowe, Sues & Reisz, 2011, and it is described in detail by Marsh & Rowe (2018). A skull, originally identified as *Massospondylus* by Attridge *et al.* (1985), was referred to as this taxon. These represent the earliest sauropodomorph skeletons described from North America.

Phylogenetic analyses demonstrate, firstly, that the North American Early Jurassic sauropodomorphs *Anchisaurus*, *Sarhsaurus* and *Seitaad* do not form a single clade (Fig. 1B) and, secondly, that after the end-Triassic mass extinction, three different dispersals events brought these sauropodomorphs into North America (Rowe *et al.*, 2011; confirmed by more detailed cladogram in Apaldetti *et al.*, 2021).

3.1.11. *Anchisauripus* – sauropodomorph or theropod?

Lull (1904a) made a detailed revision of the footprints from the Connecticut Valley (see also Lull, 1904b, 1915, 1953). He referred the makers of most of the bipedal trackways to dinosaurs, mainly saurischians plus a few ornithischians, the latter of which is still not represented by bones from the Connecticut Valley (citation of some teeth by McHone [2004: 25] is incorrect). He erected the new genus *Anchisauripus* for three-toed footprints that, following Cope (1870a, b) and Marsh (1892, 1896a), were supposedly made by *Anchisaurus*. The interpretation of the ichnotaxon *Anchisauripus* as footprints of prosauropods was not questioned until they were shown by Baird (1957) to probably be those of a small *Coelophysys*-like theropod dinosaur (Fig. 14I) (i.e., Coelophysoidea, but not including Dilophosauridae, see Hendrickx *et al.*, 2015). However, there is a continuum based on size, so it is hard to separate the footprint genera *Grallator*, *Anchisauripus*, *Eubrontes* and *Gigantipus* with increasing size (Olsen *et al.*, 1998). As Olsen (2017b: 15) notes, “the reconstructed foot skeleton of *Eubrontes giganteus* trackmaker, assuming that the toe pads were directly below the toe bones (arthral pad model), is consistent with a theropod and is indistinguishable from the non-coelophysoid *Dilophosaurus wetherilli*” (Figs 14I-L; also, Rainforth, 2003). Although the bones of *Dilophosaurus* are not known from the Connecticut Valley, footprints of *Eubrontes* occur at a horizon about 20 feet below and a few hundred yards west of the original site for *Dilophosaurus* in the Kayenta Formation (Lower Jurassic, Arizona; Welles, 1971, 1984; Marsh & Rowe, 2020). There are also hundreds of other *Eubrontes* tracksites in this formation (Milner & Kirkland, 2007). However, Weems (2003, 2006) argued that the abundant footprints of *Eubrontes* (and *Gigantipus*) were made by large early sauropodomorphs similar to *Plateosaurus* (Figs 14G, M) or by *Anchisaurus* (Figs 14A-C; including *Ammosaurus*, Weems, 2019). As such these would provide a large base of herbivores to support a normal food pyramid for the terrestrial Lower Jurassic of the Connecticut Valley. However, *Anchisaurus* was probably only facultatively bipedal (Galton, 1976), a very unlikely maker of *Eubrontes* trackways in which manus imprints are extremely rare, there being only one pair for all the *Eubrontes* trackways at DSP (Galton, 2002; Galton & Farlow, 2003; Farlow & Galton, 2003). *Kayentapus minor* from the Norian (Upper Triassic) of Virginia are attributed to manus prints of a ceratosaurian theropod by Weems (2006), who discussed the few examples of manus prints of early Mesozoic theropods. Olsen (2017b: 15) noted that the argument of Weems “requires a nearly complete lack of correspondence between pad structure and osteology, which I regard as a very unparsimonious hypothesis, given the apparently simple and excellent fit between the skeleton of

Dilophosaurus and that reconstructed for *Eubrontes*” (Figs 14K, L; also, Rainforth, 2003; Farlow *et al.*, 2018, 2022). The implications of a non-theropod “prosauropod” identity for the brontozoid ichnotaxa *Anchisauropus-Eubrontes-Gigantipes* continuum implies, firstly, that there were no theropods in the Lower Jurassic strata of Eastern North America, secondly, that early sauropodomorphs were the most common dinosaur and, thirdly, that *Otozoum* footprints were not made by a “prosauropod” (Olsen, 2017b). However, as discussed by Olsen (2017b: 17; see also Rainforth, 2003; Milan *et*

al., 2008; Farlow *et al.*, 2022), the most parsimonious hypothesis for *Otozoum* trackways is that they were made by a “prosauropod” walking with a more plantigrade posture than *Plateosaurus* (Figs 14G, H). This is indicated by “the primitive retention of a full complement of phalanges in pedal digit IV, the apparent raised and non-imprinted digit I of the hand, the large size of the tracks, and proportional similarities to Early Jurassic prosauropods.” Weems (2019) points out that the known stratigraphic range of *Eubrontes* tracks (Norian-Toarcian) happens to fall entirely within the known stratigraphic range

Fig. 14. Pes (A, B right in ventral view, C-G, I-K left in dorsal view) and osteological reconstructions for left prints using arthral-reconstructions (H, L, M). A-F: early sauropodomorph dinosaurs from Portland Formation of Manchester, Conn. A-B: YPM VP 1883, neotype of *Anchisaurus polyzelus* (Hitchcock, 1865) and holotype of *A. colurus* Marsh, 1891; and C-F: YPM VP 208, holotype of *Ammosaurus major* (Marsh, 1889), C, reconstructed pes; D-E: left pes (right reversed) as preserved, D, metatarsus and E, phalanges (cf. Fig. 5C), and F, left pes as preserved [for larger photographs see Huene (1906) and Galton (1976)]. G, early sauropodomorph *Plateosaurus* (Upper Triassic, Germany); H, footprint of *Otozoum moodi* with reconstructed arthral-model for pes which is very similar to those of early sauropodomorphs (A-G). I-K: theropods, I, *Syntarsus rhodesiensis* (Lower Jurassic, Zimbabwe), pes very similar to *Coelophysus*; J-K: *Dilophosaurus wetherelli*, J, as preserved and K, reconstructed; L, arthral-model for footprint of *Eubrontes giganteus*, ACM ICH 15/3; M, left *Plateosaurus* pes placed in *Eubrontes giganteus* footprint following Weems (2003). Photographs for A, D-F taken by PMG and B, C, G-M modified from Olsen (2017b, figs S1.3, S1.4). Scale bars = 50 mm (A-I) and 100 mm (J-M).

of bipedal “prosauropods” (Upper Carnian-Toarcian). However, the latter is the *worldwide* range whereas the bones of early sauropodomorphs from North America are restricted to the same early Early Jurassic (Hettangian) units (Portland, McCoy Brook, Navajo Sandstone) as for *Otozoum* and other tracks that are regarded as those of early sauropodomorphs (Rainforth, 2003; Olsen, 2017b). If the relative abundance of footprints reflects the relative abundance of trackmakers in the living fauna, identification of the maker of *Eubrontes* as a theropod dinosaur similar to *Dilophosaurus*, rather than an early sauropodomorph, suggests the possibility of a substantial relative abundance of large theropods in the living fauna. However, a note of caution is warranted. It is not unusual for footprints and trackways attributed to theropods to outnumber those of sauropodomorphs and ornithischians in ichnofaunas, possibly due to greater activity on the part of big meat-eaters than plant-eaters (cf. Pérez-Lorente, 2015; Leonardi & Carvalho, 2021), in which case the relative abundance of *Eubrontes* might be an artifact. On the other hand, even in well-sampled dinosaurian skeletal faunas the abundance of specimens of large theropods compared with those of large herbivorous dinosaurs can be greater than expectations based on modern mammalian faunas (Farlow *et al.*, 2023), a plausible explanation for which being that large theropods often relied on prey species other than, or in addition to, big herbivorous dinosaurs. Given the end-Triassic extinction of the tropical semiaquatic carnivores, such as phytosaurs and large labyrinthodont amphibians (although there are post-Triassic temnospondyl amphibians, viz., brachyopids in Central and Eastern Asia and chigutisaurids in South Africa and Australia, see Maisch & Matzke, 2005: 287-8) and the rarity of terrestrial herbivores, it is possible that there was an extremely unusual, inverted food pyramid for the Early Jurassic of eastern North America, with terrestrial carnivores outnumbering herbivores rather than the reverse, normal situation. The terrestrial theropod carnivores of the Connecticut Valley may have fed occasionally or even mostly on fish, as did those of the same age in western North America (see Thorpe, 1936; Milner & Kirkland, 2007; McDonald, 2010; Olsen, 2017b; Getty *et al.*, 2017; Getty, 2018). By the late Early Jurassic to Middle Jurassic, herbivorous dinosaurs became more numerous than carnivores in continental large-vertebrate faunas, and a normal terrestrial food pyramid was established.

3.2. Theropoda, Neotheropoda

Two early groups of Neotheropoda, the Coelophysoidea and Dilophosauridae, are the only theropod dinosaurs known from the Lower Jurassic (see Hendrickx *et al.*, 2015: 15, fig. 1). Coelophysoidea “encompasses small to medium sized theropods (2-6 m long) with slender

skulls, and lightly built, gracile, and elongated bodies characterized by elongated cervical centra.” The best-known species is *Coelophysis bauri*, which is represented by hundreds of articulated skeletons from a bone bed in the Upper Triassic of Ghost Ranch, New Mexico (Fig. 15I; see Colbert, 1984; Reinhart *et al.*, 2009). *Coelophysis* (*Syntarsus*) *kayentakatae* (Rowe, 1989) is known from a skull and partial skeleton (MNA V2623) plus other fragmentary specimens from the Kayenta Formation (Lower Jurassic) of Ward Terrace in the Little Colorado River Valley, Arizona. The holotype of *Coelophysis* (*Syntarsus*) *rhodensis* (Raath, 1969, 1977; for discussion of synonymy see Bristowe & Raath, 2004) is an almost complete articulated postcranial skeleton (plus hundreds of disarticulated bones) from the Forest Sandstone (Lower Jurassic) near Bulawayo, Zimbabwe. Dilophosaurids are slightly larger, more heavily built forms (2-6 m) with a slightly more derived skull and a proportionally shorter neck. The best represented species is *Dilophosaurus wetherilli* from the Kayenta Formation (Lower Jurassic) of Arizona which is known from several articulated skeletons (Fig. 15H; Welles, 1984; Marsh & Rowe, 2020).

3.2.1. Coelophysoidea: Podokesaurus holyokensis

Although there are innumerable footprints attributed to theropod dinosaurs from the Lower Jurassic of the Connecticut Valley (Lull, 1904a, 1915, 1953; Olsen *et al.*, 1998; Farlow *et al.*, 2018), bones of these animals are extremely rare.

1. *Podokesaurus holyokensis* Talbot, 1911 (Greek for “swift-footed lizard”) is based on a partial skeleton (Figs 15A-C) of a small individual (body length ~1.15 m). It was discovered in 1910 close to the campus of Mount Holyoke College in South Hadley, Mass. (map locality 22, Lull, 1953: 67) by Miss Mignon Talbot. It was in a glacially transported boulder of sandstone of the Longmeadow Formation that came from the Holyoke Range about 2 to 3 miles north of the college. Huene (1914d) provided notes and a natural sized drawing of the bones *in situ* on the slab. He erected the family Podokesauridae which included *Coelophysis* (also Huene, 1932, 1956). Lull (1915, 1953) utilized the description of Talbot (1911), with additional observations and drawings of the holotype, and provided a skeletal restoration (Fig. 15C). While the holotype slab was at the YPM, a cast (YPM VP 314; Fig. 15A) and a lantern slide (Lull, 1953, pl. 8) were made. This is extremely fortunate because the holotype was subsequently destroyed when Williston Hall, which housed the Mount Holyoke College Museum, was burnt down in 1916 (Lull, 1953). A discussion concerning the extreme anterior extent of the pubis

was summarized by Shufeldt (1916; Heilmann, 1913, 1927: 169, fig. 120.7, fig. 121 a photograph of pubis supplied by R. S. Lull; discussion briefly noted by Lull, 1953: 140, footnote 2). Huene (1932: 35-36, pl. 49, fig. 2) gave measurements, brief notes and a skeletal reconstruction. Baird (1957) concluded that a *Coelophysys*-like theropod made the footprints of *Anchisauripus* (see Olsen *et al.*, 1998; Rainforth, 2007; Farlow *et al.*, 2018).

2. A sandstone block (Fig. 15D) from the Portland Formation (Fig. 1A) from a quarry in Middletown, northern Connecticut (Colbert & Baird, 1958), with a natural cast of the pubis, tibia and ribs, was discovered by Prof. William R. Rogers. He found it among stones shipped to Newport, Rhode Island for use in the construction of Fort Adams (Guinness, 2003). Rogers (1860, 1865) published abstracts and distributed plaster casts of the block to various

Fig. 15. A-C: Coelophysoid theropod dinosaur *Podgeosaurus holyokensis* Talbot, 1911, partial skeleton found in South Hadley, Mass., A, YPM VP 314, cast of holotype, in right lateral view, photograph by PMG; B, detail of main part of body of holotype specimen (destroyed by fire), from Talbot (1911) and C, skeletal reconstruction in left lateral view, unshaded parts restored, from Lull (1915). D, plaster cast of slab of Portland Sandstone from Middletown, Conn. of a coelophysoid theropod (YPM VP 3912 of BMS MOS 2001.248) showing bone casts of the proximal and distal parts of the right pubis (large, horizontally placed bone, proximal break beyond which bone twisted relative to small proximal part of bone), right tibia (large oblique bone, note gap between proximal and distal portions) and several incomplete ribs, photograph by YPM VP. E-G: theropod dinosaur teeth (?Dilophosauridae) from Shuttle Meadow Formation of Bluff Head, North Guildford, Conn., E-F: DSP McDonald Collection, E, basal side view to show absence of denticles on anterior edge (photograph supplied by P. E. Olsen) and F, side view to show denticulate posterior edge (photograph supplied by B. Cornet); G, another similar tooth in side view (BRCM 2017. 11. 57, McDonald Collection, photograph supplied by D. Ksepka). H-I: skeletal reconstructions of theropod dinosaurs in left lateral view, kindly supplied by G. Paul who retains the copyright: H, *Dilophosaurus wetherilli* from Lower Jurassic of Arizona and I, *Coelophysys bauri* from Upper Triassic of New Mexico. Scale bars = 300 mm (A), 100 mm (B), 25 mm (D) and 10 mm (E-G); length of body ~1.25 m (C), 6 m (H) and 3 m (I).

museums (e.g., AMC 11793c, MCZ 2768, YPM VP 3912 Fig. 15D). Colbert & Baird (1958) described the original specimen, with a photo of one of the plaster casts (AMNH FARB 7636), and they concluded that it probably represents a large individual (body length 2.5 to 3 m) of *Podokesaurus holyokensis*. The original arkosic slab, which was in the collection of the Boston Society of Natural History (BSNH 13656) and is currently exhibited at the Boston Museum of Science (now BMOS.2001.248), was fully described by Getty & Bush (2011; color photo Olsen, 2017a, fig. 36C).

The two Connecticut Valley specimens fall near the extreme ends for the size range present in the coelophysoid dinosaur *Coelophysis bauri*, which is represented by hundreds of articulated skeletons from a bone bed in the Upper Triassic of Ghost Ranch, New Mexico (Fig. 15I; see Colbert, 1984; Reinhart *et al.*, 2009). *Podokesaurus holyokensis* was referred to *Coelophysis* as *C. holyokensis* (Talbot, 1911) by Colbert & Baird (1958; also, Colbert, 1964b). However, given the difference in age (15 Ma younger, Lower Jurassic versus Upper Triassic) and the incompleteness of the holotype, Colbert (1984) decided that it was better to keep *Podokesaurus holyokensis* as a separate taxon. Olsen (2017a) regards it as a coelophysoid-grade theropod.

3.2.2. *Dilophosauridae* indet.

The discovery of a tooth of “*Coelophysis*” (Figs 15E, F; McDonald Collection, on exhibition at DSP) was reported by Galton (1976; also Anon, 1980). It was collected in 1970 by Bruce Cornet from a black shale, formed from deposits in the deeper portion of a perennial lake. This shale was exposed in a stream cut in the lower Shuttle Meadow Formation (Fig. 1A, Early Jurassic, Hettangian) on the north face of Totoket Mountain in the Bluff Head Preserve (Anon, 1980) of the Nature Conservancy in Connecticut in North Guildford, Conn. (a few miles east of North Branford that is map locality 43, Lull, 1953: 68). This is locality 1 of Cornet *et al.* (1973) and McDonald (2010, fig. 5-36) gives a photograph of himself in the quarry pit. These beds produced thousands of excellently preserved fish (see McDonald, 2010: 48-53; see McDonald, 2010: 48-53). This small carnivorous theropod tooth was finally illustrated by McDonald (2010, fig. 5-37). Another similar but less well-preserved tooth (Fig. 15G; McDonald Collection, BR 217.11.57) from the same locality is illustrated by Olsen (2017a, fig. 30). These teeth represent the earliest dinosaur remains reported to date from the Connecticut Valley.

For these two teeth (Figs 15E-G; McDonald pers. comm.; Fig. 15G; D. Ksepka pers. comm.), the crown lengths are ~20 (without lost tip) and 20 mm, the maximum basal crown widths (BCW, fore-aft crown widths) are 7.2

and 7 mm, and there are 4 and ~3 denticles per mm on the posterior edge, and none on the anterior edge (Fig. 15E). The absence of serrations on the anterior edge is probably an individual variation because this occurs on upper maxillary tooth 2 and lower dentary tooth 8 in *Coelophysis* with both edges lacking serrations for teeth more anteriorly and possessing them more posteriorly (Colbert, 1989: 71; see also Buckley & Currie, 2014). In *Dilophosaurus* Welles (1984) notes that, for the larger holotype specimen with a body length of 6 m (Fig. 15H), the convex anterior edge of a dentary tooth is serrated only near the tip, the posterior border has 30 serrations per 10 mm, and the BCW is 10 mm. On this basis, the body length of the Connecticut Valley animals that shed the teeth is ~4 m. Most of the characters of the dentition-based phylogeny of Hendrickx & Mateus (2014) are based on tooth rows or are not shown by the Bluff Head teeth. An exception is the proportion of the denticles, with the fore-aft length being greater than the basal-apical height in *Dilophosaurus*, as in the Bluff Head teeth (Fig. 15F), versus being equal in the teeth of *Coelophysis*. On this basis these teeth are tentatively referred to the Dilophosauridae.

3.2.3. *Supposed bones described by McMenamin (2021a, b)*

McMenamin (2021a) reported finding several rounded clasts (eroded pieces) of Sugarloaf Arkose (=Sandstone, Upper Triassic) in the fill exposed during the repair of the parking lot at the Newman Center of the University of Massachusetts at Amherst. These clasts included a large (maximum width 123 mm), roughly triangular piece of fossilized bone. This was identified as the eroded distal end of a right humerus of a large theropod dinosaur with an estimated body length of over 9 m. It was presumed to be from the Portland Formation (Lower Jurassic), not the Sugarloaf Sandstone, but this cannot be confirmed due to the complete absence of any attached rock. Bone without any enclosing matrix is an anomaly for the Newark Supergroup in which the matrix is very well consolidated, being much harder than the bone, so once exposed the bone is eroded rather than the enclosing rock (Figs 15D, 18C-G). Indeed, it is extremely difficult to mechanically remove rock from bones in the Portland Formation (Figs 1F, 5, 6A-C, 8A-D, 16A, B). However, P. E. Olsen (pers. comm. 2021) notes that the specimen is not bone because the EDS spectrum (McMenamin, 2021a, fig. 3) shows that it is composed almost entirely of silicon and oxygen. There are only trace amounts of phosphorus and calcium whereas for bone there should be huge peaks for these elements, with or without carbon depending on the degree of preservation of organic matter in the bone. Complete replacement of bone almost never occurs and certainly not with the trabecular spaces left unfilled by a mineral

such as calcite. P. E. Olsen also notes that no thin sections are provided to demonstrate histologically that the specimen is bone and no apomorphies are cited to link it to theropod dinosaurs. However, because the EDS results are completely incompatible with calcium phosphate (as hydroapatite), he concludes that the specimen is not bone but some kind of silica foam, either a purposely made material or a byproduct of some industrial process such as the formation of slag, the solid non-metallic waste matter produced when metal is separated from ore during smelting.

McMenamin (2021b, figs 1, 3) also reported finding a small loose slab, presumed to be from the Portland Formation, in his garden in South Hadley, Mass. One side of the slab supposedly shows dinosaurian bone but no outlines are indicated or any characters given to identify it as bone, and the scanning electron microscopic image is not that of cortical/vitreous dinosaur bone. Additional bone material, interpreted as the wrist region of a non-pterodactyloid pterosaur, is shown in a cross-section on the side of the slab (McMenamin, 2021b, figs 2, 4). However, the photograph and μ CT scan of the specimen are not clear, and the outlines of the unlabeled bones are not indicated. S. C. Bennett (pers. comm. 2021) notes that the estimated wingspan of 40 cm is very small and, as a hatchling *Rhamphorhynchus* has a 30 cm span (Wellnhofer, 1975), a 40 cm individual would have quite immature bone tissue. However, McMenamin (2021b) described the bone material as being dense and thicker than is typical for later pterosaurs, which he presumed was because this was an early stage in the development of hollow bones. This is incorrect because the earliest pterosaurs have bone walls that are as thin as in any other pterosaur (K. Padian pers. comm., 2021). Bennett and Padian are not convinced that the material represents a pterosaur and agree that it needs to be better prepared and illustrated, with details of the histology, before this identity is established. Bennett also notes that the supposed pterosaur tooth (McMenamin, 2021b, fig. 6) on a loose slab of Portland sandstone found near the beach grounds in South Hadley, has a polygonal base that is not known in any pterosaur tooth. Striae do occur but, as it was not found with pterosaur bones and no evidence is provided to rule out fish or a non-pterosaur tetrapod tooth interpretation, it is an indeterminate vertebrate tooth.

3.3. Archosaurian (?dinosaurian) reptiles

Three early records of isolated bones from the Lower Jurassic of the Connecticut Valley cannot be identified more positively than those of large archosaurian (?dinosaurian) reptiles. These are the natural casts (Figs 1C-E) described by Hitchcock (1841, pl. 46, figs 69-72) from Ellington (next to East Windsor), Conn. (near map locality 30, Lull, 1953: 68; YPM VP since lost, Lull, 1953). A fragment (YPM VP 6281, since lost, D.

Brinkman pers. comm., 2018) was discovered in 1875 by Solon Wiley in the Longmeadow Sandstone (as Sugarloaf Arkose) half a mile north of Greenfield, Mass. (map locality as ?, Lull, 1953: 67; not *Anchisaurus contra* Weishampel & Young, 1996: 107). Lastly, the imperfect fragments noted by Emerson (1898) from Belchertown, Mass. (map locality 11, Lull, 1953: 67).

3.4. Crocodylomorpha, Protosuchia: *Stegomosuchus longipes*

The remains (AMC 900; Fig. 16) of a small animal (body length 25 to 30 cm) were found in the 1890s in the Longmeadow Sandstone of Hines Quarry (now Hoover Quarry), about a mile east of the village of Longmeadow, Mass. (map locality 28, Lull, 1953: 67). It was described by Emerson & Loomis (1904) and referred to the genus *Stegomus* Marsh, 1896b (for details see Section 4.2) as *S. longipes*. They noted that “all but a thin interrupted film of bone has been leached out, leaving spaces which are filled with calcite. It is, then, largely a cast, [with] both the upper and lower surfaces of the bone impressed on one block or the other.” These include both sides of the dorsal dermal armor and of the roof of the skull plus most of the limb bones (Figs 16A, B). A photo of the block with the dorsal impression was given by Emerson & Loomis (1904, with a restoration of the skull from the ventral impression) and by Lull (1915, with restoration of skull based on the dorsal impression), and photos of both blocks by Lull (1953). Lull (1912, 1915, 1953) illustrated a restored statuette of *Stegomus longipes*. *Stegomus arcuatus* Marsh, 1896b is based on a cast of dorsal dermal armor from the Upper Triassic of Fair Haven (see Section 4.2). Huene (1914d) redescribed *Stegomus longipes*. He made it the type species of *Stegomosuchus* Huene, 1922 as *S. longipes* (Emerson & Loomis, 1904) of the family Stegomosuchidae. The skull (Fig. 16D) was reinterpreted by Walker (1968, fig. 2A), who concluded that *Stegomosuchus* is not an aetosaur but a juvenile individual of an early terrestrial cursorial crocodylomorph (Walker, 1970; Whetstone & Whybrow, 1983). It is related to *Protosuchus* from the Lower Jurassic of Arizona, Nova Scotia and southern Africa (see Colbert & Mook, 1951; Crompton & Smith, 1980; Bushby & Gow, 1984; Sues *et al.*, 1996). Lull (1904b, 1915, 1953) correlated this small, apparently agile cursorial animal with the ichnotaxon *Batrachopus gracilis* (see Olsen & Padian, 1989; Rainforth, 2007; Olsen, 2017b: 21-22, fig. S1-8).

4. UPPER TRIASSIC SKELETAL REMAINS

With the discovery of a non-dinosaurian reptile in 1888, the horizon for most new skeletal discoveries

in the Connecticut Valley shifted to lower down in the Newark Supergroup, to the older New Haven Formation (=Arkose; Upper Triassic, Fig. 1A) of the Hartford basin of Connecticut. Most of the formation is pre-latest Rhaetian, the age of the End Triassic Extinction Event at 201.564 Ma (Olsen, 2017a). For photos of life size models in color of the animals concerned on exhibition at DSP, see McDonald (2010); for line drawing skeletal reconstructions, see Sues & Fraser (2010).

4.1. *Phytosauria incertae sedis*: “*Belodon*” *validus*

The first bone, the proximal part of a large right scapula (Figs 17B-F; YPM VP 2138) consists of a thin layer of bone covering a sandstone core. It was discovered in 1888 in the middle part of the New Haven Formation at Simsbury, Conn., in the quarry of Orestes Wilcox, half a mile southwest of the railroad station (map locality 42, Lull, 1953: 68). Marsh (1893) mentioned the presence of a large *Belodon*, *B. validus*, in the lower sandstone and later, based on the size of the holotype of *B. arcuatus*

Fig. 16. Protosuchian crocodylomorph *Stegomosuchus longipes* (Emerson & Loomis, 1904) from Longmeadow Formation of Longmeadow, Mass., holotype AMC 900, a split slab showing: A, external and B, internal impressions of skull roof and dermal plates of cervical and dorsal regions plus some of the limb bones. Photographs taken by PMG. C-D: restorations in dorsal view of C, skeleton, from Emerson & Loomis (1904) and D, skull, from Walker (1968). Scale bars = 20 mm (A-C) and 10 mm (D).

(see below as *Stegomus*), he estimated the length of the animal to be about 12 to 15 feet (Marsh, 1896b; so, about 7.5 feet or 225 cm with lower estimate of Baird, 1986). McGregor (1906: 95) included this species in the phytosaurian (=parasuchian) genus *Rutiodon* (Fig. 17A). Although Lull (1915, fig. 2) finally figured and described the fragmentary holotype as *Rutiodon validus* (Marsh, 1893) (Fig. 17B; mislabeled as left in Lull, 1953, fig. 10), it is really *Phytosauria incertae sedis* (Colbert, 1965). This group of aquatic predators, that resembled living crocodiles but with the external nostrils close to the orbits rather than on the end of an elongate snout with a long bony secondary palate, was removed from the Archosauria by Nesbitt (2011).

4.2. Aetosauria, Stagonolepididae: *Stegomus arcuatus*

A natural mold of the underside of the dorsal portion of the dermal armor (Figs 18C-G; YPM VP 1647; Marsh, 1896b; Lull, 1915, 1953; Lucas *et al.*, 1998, pl. 1) of a large reptile was discovered in 1895 in the middle of the New Haven Formation in a quarry near the Tomlinson bridge in Fair Haven, then part of New Haven in southern Connecticut (map locality 41, Lull, 1953: 68). Marsh (1896b) noted similarities to *Aetosaurus ferratus* Fraas, 1877, the well documented aetosaur (Figs 18A, B; see Schoch, 2007) from the Stubensandstein of Germany (now Löwenstein Formation, Upper Triassic, Norian). However, it was made the holotype of another “*Belodon*-like” reptile, *Stegomus arcuatus* Marsh,

Fig. 17. A-F: Phytosaurs from Upper Triassic. A, skeletal reconstruction (body length ~3.3 m) of *Rutiodon carolinensis* from Egypt, North Carolina, from Lull (1915). B-F: *Phytosauria incertae sedis*, *Belodon validus* Marsh, 1893, holotype YPM VP 2138 from lower New Haven Formation of Simsbury, Conn., incomplete proximal right scapula, B, restored in medial view, accuracy of impression of postero-distal part confirmed from photos taken by PMG prior to further preparation, from Lull (1915) and C-F: prepared bone in C, medial, D, posterior; E, lateral and F, proximal views, photographs taken by PMG. G-H: pre-Crocodylomorpha *Erpetosuchus*: G, *Erpetosuchus* sp., skull AMNH FARB 29300 from lower New Haven Formation, Cheshire, Conn., as preserved in right lateral view, modified from Sues *et al.* (2000), and H, *E. granti*, reconstruction of skull in right lateral view, from the Lossiemouth Sandstone Formation of northeastern Scotland, modified from Newton (1894). Abbreviations: A, antorbital opening or fenestra; D, dentary; L, laterotemporal opening or fenestra; M, maxilla; MF, mandibular fenestra; O, orbit; scale bars = 50 mm (B-F) and 10 mm (G, H).

1896b [Greek for “armored mouse”, possibly based on similar appearance to a chiton (a marine mollusk), the *mus marinus* of Pliny, or to a *musculus*, an armored shed used by Julius Caesar against the walls of Gallic towns (Baird, 1986)]. The length of the preserved carapace is ~440 mm (Figs 18C-E) and Marsh (1896b) estimated the body length at about 8 to 10 ft, but it was probably only about 5 ft or 150 cm long (Baird, 1986). Hay (1902) referred it to the Stagonolepidae (within the Aetosauria)

and Huene (1914d), who redescribed *Stegomus arcuatus*, referred it to the Aetosauria. Lucas *et al.* (1998) briefly re-describe the holotype, along with referred specimens from the Upper Triassic (Norian) of New Jersey (Passaic Formation, see Jepsen, 1948; Baird, 1986), North Carolina (lower Sanford Formation, see Parker, 1966; Huber *et al.*, 1993, fig. 5), and New Mexico (Bull Canyon Formation of Chinle Group, see Heckert & Lucas, 1998). The main block of YPM VP 1647 (Figs 18C-E) is a natural

Fig. 18. A-B: Aetosaur *Aetosaurus ferratus* from Upper Triassic of Germany, A, skeleton in left lateral view, from Schoch (2007, which see for complete anatomy); B, left paramedian scute in dorsal view, from Wild (1989). C-G: aetosaur *Stegomus arcuatus* Marsh, 1893, holotype YPM VP 1647 from Upper Triassic of New Haven, Conn., impression of underside of cast of the 16 segmental paramedian scutes with lateral scutes (six on left and 16 on right side) of the dorsal dermal armor in C, dorsal view (from Lull in Huene, 1914d; also in Marsh, 1893; Lull, 1914, 1953); D, left dorsolateral view and E, dorsal view with dashed line (-----) indicating midline (also in E, F) and solid line (____) indicating extent of overlapping piece of matrix (see F) with impressions of dorsal surface of armor; F-G: overlapping piece of matrix in E rotated 180 degrees vertically to show impressions of dorsal dermal armor (F) and then 180 degrees horizontally to better show texture (G, dashed line indicates lateral end of paramedian scutes). D provided by YPM VP, E-G taken by PMG, scale bars = 10 mm (B), 100 mm (C-E) and 30 mm (F, G).

mold of the internal (visceral) surface of 16 articulated paired dorsal rectangular paramedian (either side of midline) plates, much wider than long (width:length 3.1-4.8) from the back and posterior neck regions, with six articulated smaller trapezoidal left and 16 right lateral plates. Baird (1986: 143) noted that also “preserved (but never yet illustrated) are two chunks of the counterpart block with natural molds of the upper surfaces of several plates, both dorsal and dorsolateral.” Lucas *et al.* (1998: 1220, 1224) mention that there are “seven matrix blocks that include portions of the mold” but also that “the pattern of [dorsal] sculpture on the scutes cannot be determined.”

YPM VP 1647 includes 12 small blocks of matrix, two of which show impressions of the dorsal surface of the dermal armor. The largest one (Figs 18E-G) shows parts of five paramedian scutes, with parts of three adjacent lateral scutes. Marsh (1896b: 60) observed that the “portions recovered [of the softer upper coarser matrix cast] show that the upper surface of the plate was rugose, but not deeply sculptured, being less marked in this respect than in the other known species of *Belodonta* (then including *Aetosaurus*, Figs 18A, B). The rough surface preserved shows no regular pattern of ornamentation, and there are no indications of a crest on any of the plates” (Figs 18F, G). However, Lull (1915, 1953: 82) noted that a plaster cast, not figured and since mislaid (D. Brinkman pers. comm., 2019), shows that the dorsal surface “is covered by tiny punctuations, in series, approximately parallel to the anterior and posterior margins of the plate, which is perpendicular to the long axis of the animal’s body. A square centimeter covers about seventy such punctuations arranged in eight rows, which gives an idea of their minuteness upon so large an animal.” However, Lucas *et al.* (1998: 1220) note that “the so-called pitting of the scutes alleged by Lull (1915, 1953) is actually porosity of the sandstone matrix, not a morphological feature. Thus this “pitting” can be seen both on the scute impressions and on the surrounding sandstone matrix.”

Lucas *et al.* (1998) noted that the aetosaurian specimens from eastern USA represent a small-bodied taxon with several distinctive characters shared with *Aetosaurus* (Figs 18A, B; see Fraas, 1877, 1907; Huene, 1920b; Wild, 1989; Schoch, 2007). In the diagnosis of *Aetosaurus* by Heckert & Lucas (2000: 1546), the dorsal paramedian scutes are “moderately wide (width/length [W:L] = 2-3.5) that possess a radial pattern of elongate pits and ridges and a low dorsal boss that does not contact the posterior margin of the scute.” *A. arcuatus* is distinguished from *A. ferratus* and *A. crassicauda* “by its minimal ornamentation on dorsal paramedian scutes, consisting of a subdued boss with a faint pattern of elongate pits and grooves; lateral margin of dorsal paramedian scutes slightly angled, with scute (scutes) wider anteriorly and narrower posteriorly [so “waisted” in front of hindlimbs]; and dorsal paramedian scutes that are up to 3.5 wider

than long; and tail that tapers rapidly posteriorly; also distinguished from *A. ferratus* by its larger size (adults up to 1.5 m body length)” (Heckert & Lucas, 2000: 1550).

This referral of *Stegomus* to *Aetosaurus* as *A. arcuatus* was not accepted by Sues *et al.* (1999), who retained *Stegomus arcuatus* as does Schoch (2007). Parker (2016) notes that the specimens of *Stegomus arcuatus* only share synapomorphies of aetosaurines (*sensu* Parker, 2007) but none with *Aetosaurus ferratus*. Furthermore, the supposed lack of dorsal ornamentation, including a dorsal eminence (boss), is not diagnostic because all the North American specimens consist of natural molds of the ventral surface of the plates that are typically smooth in aetosaurs.

The holotype of *Stegomus arcuatus* is a natural cast of the dorsal “carapace” with no bone remaining (as noted by Marsh 1896b: 60: “plates ... dissolved by infiltrating waters”), not just an impression of its ventral surface. The latter formed a natural splitting plane without which the specimen probably would have been missed. Along with the molds of a few bones from Ellington (Figs 10-R; Hitchcock, 1841, 1858) and those of a coelophysoid theropod from Middletown (Fig. 15D; Getty & Bush, 2011), it helps to explain the relative paucity of recognized boney fossils from the Connecticut Valley (see Section 3.4).

4.3. Pseudosuchia: Erpetosuchidae: *Erpetosuchus*

Until recently, *Erpetosuchus* Newton, 1894 was known from only one specimen, a skull (Fig. 17H) and partial postcranial skeleton from the Lossiemouth Sandstone Formation (usually considered Carnian, Upper Triassic) of Elgin, northeastern Scotland (Walker, 1961, 1968: fig. 2b; 1970: 367-368, fig. 12d; Benton & Walker, 1985). These remains indicate a small (body length ~2 ft or ~61 cm) lightly built, fast running (cursorial) carnivorous predator (flesh reconstruction in McDonald, 2010). However, *Erpetosuchus* is now known from the lower part of the New Haven Formation of Cheshire, Conn. The new specimen (AMNH FARB 29300), first reported by Olsen *et al.* (1996), was discovered in 1995 by Paul E. Olsen of Columbia University, New York during a field trip that he organized. The specimen consists of most of the right side of the skull (except for the roof) and mandible (lacking anterior end) (Fig. 17G) plus a few vertebrae. Olsen *et al.* (2000) tentatively regard *Erpetosuchus* as the proximate sister-taxon of the Crocodylomorpha. Ezcurra *et al.* (2017) established *Erpetosuchus* and closely related taxa as the clade Erpetosuchidae, which is most closely related to Aetosauria and the bipedal carnivorous Ornithosuchidae.

4.4. Parareptilia: Procolophonid: Leptopleuroninae: *Hypsognathus*

A 10 lb. (4.5 kg) block of sandstone (YPM VP 55831) with a natural mold of vertebrae, ribs and a partial forelimb exposed on the surface was found in June 1967 by David Bazzano and Robert Baron, then aged 12 and 7, while playing in a backyard in Meriden, central Connecticut. As a result of lectures at their school from the Peabody Museum School Service, they recognized that it might be important. Consequently, they and their families brought it into the YPM (photograph in Ostrom, 1967), to which they subsequently donated it. The original provenance is unknown but, based on a heavy mineral analysis (Griggs, 1973) and its coarseness, the sandstone probably came from the upper part of the New Haven Formation (Rhaetian, Sues *et al.*, 2000). Originally, only a natural mold was visible, the result of recent dissolution of the bone, of the articulated neck and anterior dorsal vertebrae with ribs and parts of both fore limbs visible (Fig. 19D; photograph of complete block in Ostrom, 1969b) from which a cast was made (Fig. 19E). Further preparation exposed an almost complete skull and mandible of *Hypsognathus fenneri* (photograph of skull on block in Ostrom, 1969b; skull Figs 19A, B), that was described by Sues *et al.*, 2000). *Hypsognathus fenneri* Gilmore, 1928 (Greek for “high jaw”) is based on the holotype, a partial skeleton in a block of sandstone (AMNH FARB 1676) plus additional referred material, from the upper Passaic Formation (Rhaetian) of Clifton, Passaic County, New Jersey (Colbert, 1946). The skull and jaws of the adult from Connecticut (Figs 19A, B, YPM VP 55831) and of a juvenile individual (Fig. 19C) from Norian Blomidon Formation of Nova Scotia, Canada) of *Hypsognathus fenneri* were described by Sues *et al.* (2000). They noted that *Hypsognathus* represents the latest occurrence of the parareptilian family Procolophonidae. Also, that the molar-like teeth (Fig. 19C), with the deep cheek region and lower jaws (Fig. 19B), indicate that it probably fed on tough high fiber plant material. In addition, *Hypsognathus* is closely related to *Leptopleuron* (= *Telerpeton*) from the Lossiemouth Sandstone Formation (Carnian, Upper Triassic) of Elgin, northeastern Scotland (Huene, 1920c; Walker, 1961; Benton & Walker, 1985).

4.5. Lepidosauromorpha, Sphenodontia: “*Colobops*”

In March 1965, R. G. Conrod, Jr. of Bridgeport, Conn. found a partial skull (Figs 19F, G) and a few fragmentary anterior postcranial bones in a block of sandstone that came from the upper part of the New Haven Formation (Rhaetian). The block was the result of blasting during highway construction near the junction of Routes 6a, 91 and 15 between Meriden and Middletown in central Connecticut. A photograph of this small skull (median

length ~36 mm, body length > 1 m) in ventral view prior to preparation was published by Case (1982, fig. 30-6), who identified it as a juvenile sphenodontian reptile, the group that includes the living *Sphenodon*, the tuatara of New Zealand. Conrad donated the specimen to the Museum of Natural History of Princeton University, the vertebrate paleontological collections of which were subsequently transferred to the YPM in April 1985 (see Anon, 1985; Holden, 1985). The prepared cranium (Fig. 19F, G; YPM VP PU 18835), which lacks the anterior tip of the snout, the occipital region, and the dentition, was described by Sues & Baird (1993) as an indeterminate sphenodontian lepidosauromorph. Pritchard *et al.* (2018) reconstructed the skull using 3D CT scans and described it as one of the earliest rhynchosaurs, *Colobops noviportensis* (species a Latin rendition of New Haven). The genus from Greek “shortened face”, with reference to the abbreviated but exceptionally reinforced rostrum, that forms less than a quarter of the length of the skull. In addition, the supratemporal fossae (upper skull opening) is strikingly expanded to accommodate the jaw-closing muscles that were supposedly large compared to those of any known Mesozoic or extant diapsid of a similar size. The front of the skull of the Rhynchosauria bore opposing bony beaks and the teeth were arranged in dental batteries to deal with resistant plant material, with a double row of uppers on each side with the lowers as a single row fitting in between (see Romer, 1966, figs 200, 201; Carroll, 1988, fig. 13.7). However, Scheyer *et al.* (2020) note that the skull of *Colobops* is that of a juvenile individual that was strongly compressed dorsoventrally after death, with most of the bones out of life position. They regard the skull as that of a normal sphenodontian lepidosauromorph, not a rhynchosaur, with the “reinforced snout” and the “exceptionally enlarged temporal region” the result of artifacts of preservation.

5. DINOSAURIA – WHY NUMEROUS FOOTPRINTS BUT FEW OR NO BONES?

Hitchcock (1858: 188) noted that the casts of huge tree trunks in the Portland quarries were “formed by the filling up of the mold once occupied by the plant, with sand and mud, sometimes coarser than the surrounding rock,” and that a similar loss of bone could occur to leave only a mold that, even if filled with sand, would rarely be recognizable as that of bone when exposed *in situ* in a quarry. Natural casts or pseudomorphs consisting of fine reddish sand that looked like bones (Figs 10-O-R) from Ellington, Conn. (a few miles east of East Windsor that is map locality 30, Lull, 1953: 68) were first reported by Hitchcock (1841, pl. 46, figs 70-72). Later he noted that these remains have “the exact shape of bones” and “seem to me to be casts of bones formed like those of trees in the same rock” (Hitchcock, 1858: 188). Newberry (1888:

Fig. 19. A-E: Parareptilian procolophonid *Hypsognathus fenneri*, A, B, D, E, adult individual YPM VP 55831 from Upper Triassic of Meriden, Conn., skull in A, dorsal and B, right lateral views C, juvenile individual SMP VP-2160 from Passaic Formation (Upper Triassic) of Penn., ventral or palatal view of the snout region to show differentiation of dentition into incisor-like premaxillary teeth and molar-like maxillary teeth. D-E: part of natural mold (see photograph of block in Ostrom, 1969b) showing incomplete neural arches of neck and dorsal vertebrae and right humerus (D) and cast taken from the mold (E). F-G: rhynchocephalian lepidosaur “*Colobops noviportensis*” Prichard *et al.*, 2018 (a *nomen dubium*) from New Haven Formation near Middletown, Conn., dorsal view of holotype, an incomplete skull YPM VP PU 18835 in F, dorsal and G, ventral or palatal views. Photograph A taken by PMG, B, C from Sues & Fraser (2010), D, E provided by YPM VP, and F, G kindly provided by the late Don Baird of Princeton University. Abbreviations: D, dorsal vertebrae; H, right humerus; N, neck or cervical vertebrae; scale bars = 10 mm (A-C, F, G) and 25 mm (D, E).

80) noted that in “the Portland quarries casts of the trunks and branches of trees are not unfrequently met with.” Hubert *et al.* (1982: 121) note that “numerous casts of tree trunks up to 30 cm in diameter and more than a meter long were found at the Portland quarries (Ward, 1900: 227; Rice & Foye, 1927: 61-62).” Silliman (1847) illustrated the casts, as found *in situ* in the Portland Formation of Bristol, Connecticut, of the trunks of two trees; the largest trunk had a width of about one foot and gradually tapered for about 15 feet with a few branches exposed, the length of one being over 10 feet. A four-foot section of the larger trunk was donated to Yale College. It is lost (S. Hu pers. comm., 2019) but Hickey *et al.* (2011: 612) note that the “Bristol occurrence appears to represent compressed casts with a “punk” filling, probably resulting from the weathering of a lignified trunk.” However, as regards the large “tree trunks” still *in situ* in the Portland quarries, most are filled in burrows made by reptiles, and the plant pseudomorphs may be limited to twigs and small branches (P. LeTourneau pers. comm., 2019). Such a Portland “tree trunk” exhibited on the grounds of Wesleyan University in Middletown, Conn. is actually a very large, irregularly shaped burrow showing scratch marks on the inside of the burrow, and thus was produced by an amniote tetrapod rather than by an amphibian (Olsen, 2017a, figs 36A, B). As Olsen (2017a: 32) notes, “some ornithischian dinosaurs, such as the median Cretaceous *Oryctodromeus* that would have left tracks similar to *Anomoepus* have been found as skeletons within burrows (Varricchio *et al.*, 2007 [Woodruff & Varricchio, 2011; Fearon & Varricchio, 2015, 2016]), so it is not impossible that a small dinosaur could have made this large burrow.”

The best example of a natural mold from the Connecticut Valley is the holotype (YPM VP 1647) of the aetosaur *Stegomus arcuatus* from the Upper Triassic of Fair Haven. The impression of the ventral surface of the dorsal armor formed a natural splitting plane (Figs 18C-G) and there are still a couple of pieces of matrix with impressions of the dorsal surface of this armor (see Section 4.2).

A tibia, pubis and some ribs (BSNH 13656, Fig. 15D, see Section 3.2.1) of a coelophysoid theropod dinosaur from the Portland Formation of Portland, Conn., first reported by Rogers (1860), were described by Colbert & Baird (1958) as natural casts of impressions of the bones. However, they were reinterpreted by Getty & Bush (2011) as “pseudomorphs”, with the buried bones dissolved away to leave cavities that were filled with sand (so natural casts). They postulated that the bones were dissolved in the subsurface prior to the lithification of the overlying sand bed. The decrease in pH that led to this bone dissolution probably resulted from the infiltration of naturally acidic rainwater, with possible contributions from root respiration and the decomposition of plants under oxidative conditions. They concluded that such processes would account for the non-preservation of

the bones of a *Dilophosaurus*-like large theropod, the probable maker of the abundant large prints of *Eubrontes*. The same processes could also account for the complete absence of skeletal remains of ornithischian dinosaurs [note that McHone (2004: 24) incorrectly stated that they were represented by some teeth], a group well represented by the ichnogenus *Anomoepus* (Olsen & Rainforth, 2003; Farlow *et al.*, 2018) from the Portland Formation of the Connecticut Valley.

Dates and biographical references for some of the workers cited above:

Edwin Harris Colbert (1905-2001; Anon, 2002; Dodson, 2002); Edward Drinker Cope (1840-1897; Osborn, 1929, 1931; Colbert, 1968); Edward B. Hitchcock, Sr. (1763-1864; Lesley, 1877; Colbert, 1968; Robinson, 1979; Steinbock, 1989); Edward B. Hitchcock, Jr. (1828-1911; Phillips, 1911; Anon, 2017); Friedrich von Huene (1875-1969; Colbert, 1968; Maisch, 1999, 2021); Richard Swann Lull (1867-1957; Gregory, 1957; Colbert, 1968); Othniel Charles Marsh (1832-1899; Schuchert & LeVine, 1940; Colbert, 1968; McCerran, 1993); Paul Eric Olsen (1953- ; Wailoo, 1988); John Harold Ostrom (1928-2005; Wellnhofer, 2001; Dodson & Gingerich, 2006; Dodson, 2015; Anon, 2018); Sir Richard Owen (1804-1892; Colbert, 1968; Rupke, 1994); Harry Govier Seeley (1839-1909; Colbert, 1968); Benjamin Silliman, Sr. (1779-1864; Caswell, 1877; Narendra, 1979); and Mignon Talbot (1869-1950; Weishampel & Young, 1996: 80-81, fig. 4.21).

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